

interscada

InterSCADA demo specification/D1.3

WP 1, T 1.3

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Technical references

Project Acronym	InterSCADA
Project Title	Interoperable, Scalable and seCure Ac-Dc modular Automation system
Project Coordinator	Antonello Monti Fraunhofer antonello.monti@fit.fraunhofer.de
Project Duration	October 2024 – September 2027 (36 months)
Deliverable No.	D1.3
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1 - Needs, methodologies and approaches
Task	T 1.3 – InterSCADA demo specification
Lead beneficiary	10 (SINTEF)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	3 (DERlab), 1 (Fraunhofer), 6 (IPTO), 11 (IEN), 3 (ASM), 9 (ARTEL), 7 (REE), 17 (RTE), 12 (RWTH), 5 (CIRCE)
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2025
Actual submission date	30 September 2025

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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2. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the results of task 1.3 in work package 1 (WP1) in InterSCADA: “Pilots specification: use cases, datasets and key performance indicators”.

WP1 contributes to the InterSCADA project by reviewing existing approaches for supervision and control of hybrid AC/DC systems, identifying technical and regulatory gaps to further inform the development of the InterSCADA architecture. The purpose of Task 1.3 is to ensure that the project’s demos and the algorithms developed in other WPs in InterSCADA are aligned. The task also reports and refines project and global key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the specific technical contributions of the project, such as design, control and stability of future hybrid power systems, and higher level global KPIs evaluating the project’s contributions to European decarbonizing targets.

This deliverable reports on the specification of the four InterSCADA demonstrators¹, describing the technical requirements of their use cases² as well as their intended benefits. The work in Task 1.3 has been conducted primarily by means of an iterative collaborative process among the WP1 partners. A common template for specifying the demos and their use cases has been used as a starting point, and the final specifications of the four demonstrators have been aligned and harmonized through regular meetings and iterative improvements. The work has also focused on ensuring that the KPIs defined for each of the four demos are aligned with the project-wide KPIs defined for InterSCADA as a whole. By doing so, the success of the individual demonstrators shall contribute towards the overarching project goals.

The report is structured as follows. Chapter 2 starts with a description of the methodology and process utilized in Task 1.3. The chapter then presents a high-level summary of the four demos along with a description of their datasets and models. Chapter 3 reports on the work done to align the relevant project-wide KPIs with the KPIs of the individual demos. The chapter also includes a summary of all the project-wide KPIs along with technical definitions and information needed to operationalize them. Chapters 4-7 present the full specifications developed for each of the four demos, using a standardized template. Chapter 8 concludes the report.

¹ A real-life implementation of the InterSCADA platform and one or more of the algorithms developed in the project (e.g. for monitoring, detection or control) in a physical grid with hybrid AC/DC characteristics. Four such demonstrators or “demos” are defined as part of the InterSCADA project. The terms “pilot” and “demonstrator/demo” are used interchangeably in the project application / grant agreement, but “demonstrator/demo” will be used exclusively in this deliverable.

² Variations/sub-scenarios of a demo. This can for example be over-voltage detection in a WAMPAC system.

3. InterSCADA demonstrators

3.1. Introduction

Four real-life demonstrators have been defined to enable the implementation, demonstration and validation of the InterSCADA framework and algorithms. These four demos, presented in the following subsections, will demonstrate innovative solutions for various applications, such as wide area monitoring, protection and control (WAMPAC) systems, real-time transient stability assessment, integration of LVDC systems, and system operation optimization based on AI support.

The four InterSCADA demos are part of WP5 of the project. While WP5 is concerned with the actual execution of the demos, Task 1.3 defines the use cases to be studied in each demo. Furthermore, the task ensures that the demo and use case specifications are harmonized and suited for testing the monitoring and control algorithms developed in other WPs in InterSCADA. Task 1.3. is also concerned with aligning the KPIs defined for each of the demos with the project-wide KPIs. This alignment is necessary to ensure that the success of the demos contributes to the stated goals of the InterSCADA project.

The demo specifications presented in chapters 4-7 define the four demos and their respective use cases and illustrate their exact implementation to provide technical requirements which help inform the algorithm development in WP2. The four final demo specifications, which constitute the main body of this report, are the result of an iterative collaborative process among the partners in WP1.

The specifications for the four demos have been developed and aligned by means of a common template. This template is based on IEC 62559-2 edition 1, but with some modifications made to suit the needs of this project. Most importantly, modifications have been made to align the terminology used in the templates with that which is used in the InterSCADA project. The original template is intended to be used for a single “use case” which in turn may consist of several “scenarios”. In this project the template has instead been used to describe each demo, which in turn consists of several use cases.

The following subsections of this chapter provide a summary of each demo and its use cases. Furthermore, the datasets and models associated with each demo, which are not covered by the specification templates, are described.

3.2. Demo 1 - AMI-based LV grid monitoring and inverter-based DER control integration in SCADA

3.2.1. Overview

Demo 1 aims to demonstrate the use of advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) for real-time monitoring of a hybrid AC/DC LV distribution grid in Terni, Italy. The pilot addresses the operational challenges posed by high penetration of inverter-based distributed energy resources (DERs) in LV grids. The pilot will be implemented in a part of the LV AC distribution grid which contains a new 700 V DC section. The main DC components are two LV AC/DC converters which power the bus-bar of the DC grid. The DC grid includes a storage system, a PV power plant, an electric vehicle (EV) charging station, and a power distribution for priority loads.

The demo focuses on enhanced grid observability and controllability, both of which are needed to successfully adopt a higher penetration of active, bi-directional grid elements such as DERs and storage systems. The first part of the demo focuses on improved observability to enable the implementation of advanced functionalities such as voltage regulation, demand response, and power flow control. The second part focuses on enhancing the controllability of the hybrid system through the coordinated adjustment of droop control parameters on the two AC/DC converters. The droop control parameters will be optimized in real time based on the system's load and generation profile, thereby optimizing the power and load flow across the hybrid grid. The goal is to mitigate risks such as current oscillations, voltage deviations, and overloading of individual feeders.

3.2.2. Datasets and models

Models:

- Hybrid AC/DC microgrid monitoring and control model

Datasets:

- AMI data: Voltage, current, power consumption, and frequency readings at different LV grid nodes.
- PMU and sensor data: Time-synchronized voltage and current phasors, power flow direction, and power quality indicators.
- DER-specific measurements:
 1. PV: Real-time generation data, maximum power point tracker (MPPT) output.
 2. Battery: SoC (State of Charge), charge/discharge status, voltage, and current.
 3. EV charger: Charging power, direction of power flow (V2G), operational status.
- Active front end (AFE) converters: DC voltage level, current flow direction, droop parameters.
- Critical load panel: Voltage supply status and continuity indicators.
- Protocols: Modbus TCP/IP, Modbus RTU (for field devices), MQTT (for internal microservices).

- Data storage: Time-series database connected to SCADA and InterSCADA for historical analysis and validation.
- Integration: Data is synchronized across the legacy SCADA platform and InterSCADA via APIs and internal memory-sharing mechanisms within microservices.

Table 1: Actors A in Demo 1 - External components and systems

Actor	Type	Interaction
Legacy SCADA System	System Platform	Exchanges real-time data and setpoints with InterSCADA through API & MQTT
InterSCADA Platform	System Platform	Middleware coordinating control & monitoring via microservices
PV Converter (Zekalabs)	Device	Provides generation data and receives commands (via Modbus TCP/RTU)
Battery Converter	Device	Same as above; also used for flexibility/backup
EV Charger/Vehicle	Device	Sends consumption data and receives setpoints
AC/DC Converters (AFE)	Device	Core hybrid control elements with droop control & power flow balancing
Microservices Layer	Software Module	Performs data processing, optimization, and communication
MQTT Broker	Middleware	Routes data to/from SCADA, InterSCADA, and services
System Operator	Human	Visualizes grid status and sends control commands

Table 2: Actors B in Demo 1 - Real-time monitoring of grid parameters

Actor	Type	Function in monitoring
PMUs (Phasor Measurement Units)	Device	Provide time-synchronized voltage/current phasor data — crucial for stability assessment
Smart Meters / Sensors (AMI)	Device	Monitor local voltage, power, energy usage, and PQ at the prosumer level
Local Controllers (SMPs, etc.)	Controller	Collect data from field devices and forward to microservices (or legacy SCADA)

Microservices	Software	Aggregate and process monitoring data, detect issues, and support control logic
MQTT Broker	Middleware	Transfers monitoring data between legacy SCADA, InterSCADA, and microservices

3.3. Demo 2 - Implementing WAMPAC algorithms for AC/DC hybrid power systems

3.3.1. Overview

The large-scale integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) generation with power electronics (PE) interfaces in the Hellenic Electricity Transmission System (HETS) presents new operational and stability challenges for the grid, which can be divided into three categories.

1. Changes in short circuit current levels and network topologies, which can disrupt existing protection schemes
2. Reduction of inertia, which can cause stability issues
3. Power oscillations

In addition to these challenges, the HETS will increasingly incorporate hybrid AC/DC systems. Examples of this are the high-voltage direct current (HVDC) and high-voltage alternating current (HVAC) connections between mainland Greece and the island of Crete, the upcoming HVDC connection between Corinth and the island of Kos, the HVAC interconnections between islands in the Dodecanese region and the HETS, and the new HVDC connection between Greece and Italy.

There are currently phasor measurement units (PMUs) installed in the HETS which can provide time-synchronized information with high resolution for stability management of AC/DC hybrid power systems. However, while the penetration of PMUs is increasing, more work is needed to optimize the use of data for monitoring and controlling the network.

Demo 2, which includes the existing Greece-Italy HVDC link known as GRITA, aims to demonstrate the benefits of having a WAMPAC system processing the information of an AC/DC hybrid grid in real-time, enabling the optimal operation of the grid and supporting the security analyses.

3.3.2. Datasets and models

Models:

- A set of PSS®E files (in .raw, .seq, and .dyr formats) related to the Hellenic Electricity Transmission System (HETS) is collected to test the various microservices to be implemented within the InterSCADA platform. These files collectively provide a detailed representation of the examined network. Generally, in PSS®E, the RAW format (with file extension .raw) is used to store steady-state data for power flow analyses, .seq files contain the sequence data of the system, and the DYR format (with extension .dyr) is used to store the parameters of dynamic components.

Datasets:

- PMU data from 18 PMUs installed in HETS are collected in a CSV (comma-separated values) textual format which include:

Table 3: PMU data collected in Demo 2

Actor	Type
PhasorDate	The date of the measurement
PhasorTime	The hour, minute and second of the measurement
PhasorMs	The ms of the measurement
GpsReliable	1 if GPS reliable, 0 if not
UPhase1abs	The voltage magnitude of phase 1
UPhase1phase	The voltage angle of phase 1
UPhase2abs	The voltage magnitude of phase 2
UPhase2phase	The voltage angle of phase 2
UPhase3abs	The voltage magnitude of phase 3
UPhase3phase	The voltage angle of phase 3
IPhase1abs	The current magnitude of phase 1
IPhase1phase	The current angle of phase 1
IPhase2abs	The current magnitude of phase 2
IPhase2phase	The current angle of phase 2
IPhase3abs	The current magnitude of phase 3
IPhase3phase	The current angle of phase 3
Frequency	The measured frequency

Due to the confidentiality of the models and datasets shared by IPTO to the receiving partners, a bilateral non-disclosure agreement (NDA) was signed to thoroughly describe the appropriate use of the shared data.

3.4. Demo 3 – Optimization and remedial actions for the Spanish Control Centre and the AC/DC system based on AI agents

3.4.1. Overview

Demo 3 will focus on the operation of the Spanish transmission system. One of the main challenges for Spain's TSO – Red Eléctrica de España (Red Electrica) – in integrating renewable energy and operating the transmission grid is adapting existing infrastructure and developing new solutions to manage the variability of renewable generation and ensure a secure and efficient electricity supply. The Spanish power system is undergoing large structural changes driven by integration of renewables – mainly wind and solar – and electrification of demand. This evolution introduces significant operational complexity in the real-time management of the transmission network. A key factor contributing to this complexity is the integration of HVDC links in the system and interconnections. While HVDC connections enhance the system flexibility and cross-border exchange capacity, they also change the dynamic behaviour of the grid. This, combined with the reduced system inertia and increasing decentralization of generation, introduces new requirements for the tools and procedures used by Red Electrica's control centre.

Demo 3 aims to demonstrate the use of optimization tools based on artificial intelligence (AI) to provide real-time operational decision support for network operators at the control centre. The tools will be able to identify optimal setpoints for controllable equipment, possible remedial actions, recommend topology changes, connect and disconnect voltage control equipment, and propose adjustments to power and voltage setpoints in generators, HVDC links and FACTS devices. In this way the AI tool will contribute to the optimal and reliable operation of hybrid AC/DC power systems.

3.4.2. Datasets and models

Models:

- Grid model: electrical model of the transmission system including all the descriptive information such as bus connectivity, line impedances, equipment ratings and operational constraints. The format of the grid model will be RAW format or equivalent (typical model used to store steady-state data for power system analysis).
- Models of the DC controllable elements incorporated in the system: specific models that define the operation modes of the controllable DC elements tested in the use case will be used. For example, HVDC models with different operation modes.

Datasets:

- Data from the state estimator: information of the different states of the power system over time (in .raw format or similar) required for the use case evaluation (demand, generation, system topology, voltage, current, power, etc.)
- SCADA/EMS historical data: historical measurements from power system (voltage, current, active and reactive power, network topology status, etc.) in open format with

15min granularity. Used to define representative scenarios for analysis and train and validate the algorithms developed within the project.

- Contingencies: list and characteristics of the different network contingencies that are of interest to be considered and analysed for secure system operation.
- Operator actions log: historical records of actions taken by system operators in response to system operation or contingency events. Used as input for training and validating algorithms developed in the project.
- AI-generated setpoints and remedial actions: outputs generated by the optimization and AI algorithms, for example, proposed control actions, equipment setpoints and topological reconfigurations.
- Operator feedback on proposed actions: feedback from human operators regarding the actions proposed by the AI system, including acceptance, rejection, or adjustment of recommendations

3.5. Demo 4 - Enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis on the French AC/DC system

3.5.1. Overview

Demo 4 aims to assess the impact of power-electronics-interfaced renewable generation and DC components on AC transient stability of the French transmission system. The large-scale integration of renewable generation and HVDC links results in a profound shift in the dynamics of the existing AC power system. The grid is evolving into a hybrid network, combining large centralized conventional generators with numerous small, distributed generation units and significant loads connected via AC/DC converters. Concurrently, cross-border connections and power exchanges are rapidly expanding due to the significant growth of DC links (with Spain, Italy and UK in the French case for example).

This evolution leads to increasingly volatile operating conditions, making it difficult to predict all potentially dangerous contingencies and significantly impacting grid stability. Risky situations are emerging under a growing range of operating conditions, yet they remain challenging to anticipate. To ensure reliability in such a dynamic and volatile grid, predetermined stability limits must be highly restrictive, resulting in increased operational costs. Consequently, the current practice of France's TSO - RTE, which relies on fixed, predetermined limits, is no longer adequate to keep pace with the evolving grid landscape. In addition, the behaviour of new (DC) components—such as DC grids and power-electronics-interfaced resources—now plays a significant role in the overall dynamics of the power system. Recent grid code modifications reinforce this need by requiring such installations not only to ride through faults but also, in some cases, to actively support system stability—for example, by injecting reactive current during disturbances.

Demo 4 will therefore demonstrate the importance and advantages of an enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis of a fast-evolving hybrid AC/DC system. It will make use of intelligent and state-of-the-art individual modules reducing the needs for costly time-domain simulations and considering AC and DC components behaviours.

3.5.2. Datasets and models

Models:

- Regarding the models, the new decision-making process for transient stability analysis will be evaluated on the French power system, including both Extra High Voltage and High Voltage networks (from 400 kV down to 63 kV). The demonstration will be conducted on a large-scale system comprising approximately 10 000 lines, 2 000 transformers and 6 000 substations.
- The models used will include static system characteristics – such as network topology and line/transformers parameters – as well as RMS detailed dynamic models for conventional generation units and their control systems, power-electronic-interfaced resources, DC links and associated protection schemes (e.g. out of step protections). In addition to full-detail modelling, simplified representations will be incorporated into

specific stages of the process. For instance, the filtering phase using the Extended Equal Area Criterion (EEAC) method will rely on reduced models. Network reduction and aggregation techniques will be developed during the project to enable scenario-specific simplifications, avoiding the need for full-detail modelling in every case. Proprietary dynamic models for generation units will be used and cannot be shared with other project partners. However, simplified or equivalent models may be provided if required.

Datasets:

- Regarding the data, the demonstration will utilize historical operational data sourced from RTE's SCADA/EMS system. Measurements and system snapshots will be exchanged between the data historian and the InterSCADA platform. This dataset includes active and reactive power (P, Q), voltage (U), and system configuration data as described earlier.

The demonstration is expected to run continuously over a defined period—such as a representative summer period—and will also include the analysis of selected individual snapshots.

4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The work in task 1.3 has in part consisted of ensuring that the KPIs developed for the four demos are aligned with the KPIs defined by the InterSCADA project proposal. The fulfilment of the demo KPIs should result in fulfilment of the relevant InterSCADA KPIs. This chapter summarizes how all the project KPIs shall be reached during the project, with special emphasis on the alignment of the project KPIs and the KPIs developed for each of the four demos.

4.1. KPIs to be addressed by Task 1.3 and the four demos

Table 4 lists all the project KPIs in InterSCADA. The project KPIs marked in bold text in Table 4 were identified as relevant for Task 1.3 and should be addressed directly by Task 1.3 and the demos.

Table 4: List of project KPIs with responsible task(s). Bold entries are addressed by Task 1.3 and the four demos (Tasks 5.2 – 5.5)

KPI	Description	Responsible task	Contributor(s)
KPI 1.1	≥ 6 modular microservices integrated in the service layer of InterSCADA platform;	Task 2.3	Task 3.1
KPI 1.2	≥ 10 data structures integrated in the GUI	Task 3.5	Task 3.4, Demos
KPI 1.3	≥ 4 external legacy systems (≥1 per demonstrator) interconnected with InterSCADA platform via dedicated API	Task 3.4	
KPI 2.1	≥ 10 data models in the data acquisition and interoperability layer	Task 4.1	
KPI 2.2	≥ 3 cyber-attacks models formalized	Task 4.2	
KPI 2.3	≥ 50% reduction in average detection time of cyber-attack occurrence	Task 4.2	
KPI 2.4	≥ 4 transient stability models, specific for AC/DC grids, defined in the DSA tool	Task 4.3	

KPI 3.1	≥ 8 use cases based on formalized requirements for AC/DC system operations	Task 1.3	
KPI 3.2	10 of identified barriers in the current regulatory framework.	Task 6.1	Task 6.3, Task 1.2
KPI 4.1	30% Energy loss reduction in the simulated scenarios using the developed Optimal Power Flow (OPF)	Task 2.2	
KPI 4.2	20 % Voltage stability improvement using the developed OPF	Task 2.2	
KPI 4.3	30% reduction of voltage RMSE associated to the estimated states	Task 2.1	
KPI 5.1	≥ 5 instability modes detected in the Wide Area Monitoring, Protection, and Control (WAMPAC) system	Task 2.3	Task 5.3 (Demo 2)
KPI 5.2	≥ 50% reduction in average instability occurrence detection time	Task 5.5 (Demo 4)	
KPI 5.3	≥ 20% ROCOF reduction via stability countermeasures	Task 5.3 (Demo 2)	Task 2.3
KPI 5.4	≥ 5 options of setpoints and remedial actions provided by the AI artefact	Task 5.4 (Demo 3)	
KPI 6.1	≥ 30% increase of oscillations detected	Task 2.3	
KPI 6.2	≥ 20% increase of detected voltage instabilities	Task 2.3	
KPI 6.3	≥ 20% increase in the accuracy of detected RoCoFs	Task 2.1	
KPI 6.4	≥ 40% increase of detected system splits	Task 2.3	Task 5.3 (Demo 2)

KPI 6.5	≥ 15 Synchronized DC Measurement Units (DMUs) and Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) installed and integrated in the metering systems.	Task 5.2 (Demo 1)	Task 5.3 (Demo 2)
KPI 7.1	10 adaptation requirements for grid codes	Task 6.1	
KPI 7.2	15 techno-economic parameters assessed, associated with InterSCADA solutions	Task 6.3	
KPI 7.3	10% energy system cost reduction	Task 6.3	
KPI 8.1	10 key organizations actively engaged (via dissemination synergies & knowledge exchange)	Task 7.4	
KPI 8.2	50 direct contacts of potentially interested users, investors, enablers	Task 7.3	Task 6.4, Task 7.1
KPI 8.3	5 new work items as contributions (evolution/adaptation) of standards.	Task 6.1	Task 1.2

4.2. Operationalizing the KPIs

Below is a summary of how each project KPI shall be operationalized.

KPI 1.1: ≥ 6 modular microservices integrated in the service layer of InterSCADA platform

More than 6 modular microservices will be developed during WP2, such as:

- Detection of overvoltages (SINTEF)
- Detection of power oscillations (SINTEF, IEN)
- Detection of sudden changes in frequency (ROCOF monitoring) (CIRCE)
- System split monitoring (SINTEF)
- Monitoring of inertia (IEE, CIRCE)
- Protection algorithm (CIRCE, IEN)
- Frequency support using HVDC link (IEN)
- Oscillation damping (SINTEF)

RTE will execute the integration of EEAC code and of the network reduction method in the service layer of IS platform. All the services will be integrated into the INTERSCADA platform during WP3.

The plan to achieve the KPI is:

1. Develop the services during tasks of WP2
2. Integrate the services during tasks of WP3
3. Deploy the services in demonstrators during tasks of WP5

KPI 1.2: ≥ 10 data structures integrated in the GUI

The data models resulting from the survey will be included in the GUI.
The data structures will be in accordance with the data models survey for KPI 2.1.

KPI 1.3: ≥ 4 external legacy systems (≥ 1 per demonstrator) interconnected with InterSCADA platform via dedicated API

To address KPI 1.3, the ASM demonstrator focuses on integrating its existing legacy SCADA system (AVEVA System Platform) with the InterSCADA platform through the development of dedicated API-based microservices. This integration ensures bidirectional data exchange for both monitoring and control functions. Specifically, ASM is implementing a RESTful API to interface with the legacy system, along with custom Modbus and MQTT drivers within the microservices to manage data collection from hybrid AC/DC components such as AFEs, PV inverters (Zekalabs converter), batteries (Zekalabs converter), and EV chargers. The collected data is synchronized and made available in real time across both SCADA systems, enabling full observability and control. The architecture has been designed to be modular and generalizable, allowing other legacy platforms to be integrated through the same approach. This setup will be validated through end-to-end data flow tests and cross-verification of real-time parameters between systems. Coordination with other demonstrators is ongoing to ensure harmonization in approach and scalability across at least four legacy systems, thereby fully meeting the KPI requirement.

In the context of the Greek Demo, InterSCADA platform will be interconnected with one external legacy system, namely an existing PDC, with IEEE C37.118 protocol.

In the context of the French Demo, data from the data historian of RTE's current SCADA/EMS system will be transferred to the InterSCADA platform.

In the context of Spanish Demo, due to cybersecurity constraints, no direct API integration with the legacy SCADA is permitted. Instead, in the innovation phase, SCADA data will be extracted and securely transferred as structured files to the InterSCADA platform. File transfer applications or automated scripts will be used for this purpose. This method fulfils the interoperability goal while respecting national cybersecurity regulations. The transferred data will enable testing and validation of the demo functionalities at the expected TRL level.

KPI 2.1: ≥ 10 data models in the data acquisition and interoperability layer

For KPI 2.1, the project partners will be asked about their data models needed for the platform. This relates especially to the models needed for the demos in WP5. A survey will be conducted in which the data models and formats are to be entered. The survey will clarify, for example, which APIs and protocols are needed for the microservices interacting on the InterSCADA platform. The results of this survey will then be tied into the development and integration tasks of WP2 and WP3. The data models will then be deployed in demonstrators during WP5.

KPI 2.2: ≥ 3 cyber-attacks models formalized

The virtual redundancy algorithm and the second-layer ultra-fast cybersecurity channel will be tested with the simulated 3-cyber attacks including DDOS attacks, MITM attacks, data tampering, and brute force attacks. Each attack will be defined clearly in terms of its characteristics and potential impacts by ensuring security measures.

KPI 2.3: $\geq 50\%$ reduction in average detection time of cyber-attack occurrence

The detection time of cyber-attack occurrence will be reduced by developing the ultra-fast second layer blockchain solution. The improved detection time will be compared to reference values obtained from the state-of-the-art cyber-attack detection time and the standards to determine the improvement. The second layer ultra-fast (SLUF) channel is developed to reduce the transaction time of the blockchain which also improves the detection time of the cyber-attacks.

KPI 2.4: ≥ 4 transient stability models, specific for AC/DC grids, defined in the DSA tool

Proper analysis of AC/DC grids requires detailed and accurate models of the power converter devices. Simulation of these models is time-consuming, especially if done in EMT environment. On the other hand, the requirements of DSA tools are speed and robustness of response, while yielding meaningful and credible results. In this context Task 4.3 will evaluate applicability of the models for components of AC/DC grids and improve them if necessary, so that they will comply with the requirements of DSA tools. As key elements of AC/DC grids are power electronic converters, the focus will be put on representation of the following elements:

1. HVDC link based on line commutated converters (LCC HVDC)
2. HVDC link based on voltage source converters (VSC HVDC)
3. Power electronic converters for wind and solar applications
4. Battery energy storage systems (BESS)
5. Grid-forming converters

This KPI will be realized mainly in scope of Task 4.3 with supplementary contribution from Task 3.2.

KPI 3.1: ≥ 8 use cases based on formalized requirements for AC/DC system operations

The four demo specifications in chapters 4-7 define a total of 16 use cases, all of which pertain to different hybrid AC/DC systems.

KPI 3.2: 10 of identified barriers in the current regulatory framework.

This KPI will look at the analysis of the current regulatory framework associated with hybrid AC/DC systems and SCADA systems developed within D1.2 "*Regulatory and standardization framework analysis*". It will count the number of identified regulatory barriers and later compare it with the target established at the beginning of the project. It is expected to identify at least 10 regulatory barriers.

KPI 4.1: 30% Energy loss reduction in the simulated scenarios using the developed Optimal Power Flow (OPF)

The OPF will be tested on multiple simulation models of the Spanish system. The reference for calculating the energy loss reduction will be a system at an operating point which is not optimised. Particularly when the system is in an unusual or stressed state, e.g., following severe disturbances or following a black start, it can be argued that the operating point will be suboptimal w.r.t. the losses in the system. The losses in the system in a suboptimal state will be compared to the losses at the state to establish the losses reduction. This will be done for multiple simulation models and scenarios, where it is expected that at least in some of the cases, the 30% losses reduction target will be reached.

KPI 4.2: 20 % Voltage stability improvement using the developed OPF

Voltage Stability Indicators (VSIs) will be calculated for all load buses (or a representative subset, such as the weakest ones identified in the base case). The critical values to monitor are the worst-case VSIs across the network, which typically defines the voltage stability margin.

The comparison will be made between:

1. A "suboptimal" or reference operating point (e.g., pre-OPF dispatch, or a stressed condition without corrective actions).
2. The "optimized" OPF solution with corrective actions enabled.

The KPI can then be quantified as the relative improvement of the worst-case VSI. The percentwise improvement is quantified as follows:

$$\text{Improvement (\%)} = \frac{VSI_{\text{baseline}} - VSI_{\text{OPF}}}{VSI_{\text{baseline}}} \times 100$$

KPI 4.3: 30% reduction of voltage RMSE associated to the estimated states

RWTH will prepare a novel wideband PMU algorithm validated against an extended IEC/IEEE 60255-118-1:2018 standard to detect harmonic instability, a relatively new overvoltage source associated with renewables penetration capable of generating disconnection of AC and DC loads, thus triggering power losses and unstable conditions. This discriminates the fundamental frequency from other harmonics, improving the voltage estimation under challenging harmonic and interharmonic conditions (as per defined in the standard). Moreover, a novel DMU algorithm is also going to be provided, validated against common DC estimation by averaging.

Moreover, with the support of a better ROCOF estimator, presented by RWTH, the RMS error (RMSE) can be improved under dynamic conditions.

COMSENSUS is also providing PMUs and DC measurement unit (DMU) field devices in different pilot sites, improving the observability and reducing error in state-estimation against non-synchronous measurements.

The state estimation will be tested against the solutions delivered and compared to classical estimation algorithms, as well as against state estimators with low to no penetration of synchronized measurement devices.

KPI 5.1: ≥ 5 instability modes detected in the Wide Area Monitoring, Protection, and Control (WAMPAC) system

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservices developed by SINTEF and IEN during WP2 called “Detection of Power Oscillations” and implemented on the InterSCADA platform during WP3.

This KPI will be evaluated using different types of data (active power, voltage, frequency, etc.), using WP5 demonstrators' data and historical data if needed. The idea is to detect different oscillatory frequency modes with the microservices deployed on the InterSCADA platform.

KPI 5.2: ≥ 50% reduction in average instability occurrence detection time

To achieve KPI 5.2, screening methods, network reduction, and aggregation techniques will be developed within both WP2 and WP4 to accelerate model-based dynamic security analysis. These techniques will subsequently be integrated into the InterSCADA platform in WP3.

All these modules will be deployed in Demo 4 during WP5 and are expected to significantly speed up real-time transient stability analysis. The goal is to reduce computation time by half compared to a brute-force dynamic security assessment approach. This improvement will enable faster detection of risky situations, shortening the time required to identify potential instabilities and promptly initiate countermeasures to prevent system collapse.

KPI 5.3: $\geq 20\%$ ROCOF reduction via stability countermeasures

During Demo 2, a frequency support algorithm for frequency control will be investigated, providing active power set points for the GRITA HVDC link. By conducting extensive simulation scenarios using an accurate model of part of the Hellenic electricity transmission system, the ROCOF values will be compared with and without the frequency support algorithm across a series of disturbance scenarios.

First, the following parameters will be defined:

- A) System model of the Hellenic electricity transmission system based on PSS/E software
- B) Disturbance definition (faults, generator trips, etc.)
- C) Stability countermeasures (frequency support algorithm)
- D) Simulation parameters (step-time, etc.)

Then, the ROCOF reduction will be quantified using the following procedure:

- A) Base case modelling and simulation (without frequency support algorithm)
 - i) Apply disturbance
 - ii) Run a dynamic simulation
 - iii) Measure ROCOF
- B) Stability counter measurements modelling and simulation (with frequency support algorithm)
 - i) Apply disturbance
 - ii) Run a dynamic simulation
 - iii) Measure ROCOF
- C) Comparison:
 - Compare the ROCOF values from the base case and the case with frequency support to quantify the reduction achieved.

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservice developed by IEN during WP2 called “Frequency support using HVDC link” and implemented on the InterSCADA platform during WP3.

KPI 5.4: ≥ 5 options of setpoints and remedial actions provided by the AI artefact

This KPI evaluates the operational effectiveness of the AI-based SCOPF model developed within the project, focusing on its ability to generate optimized power network states considering the current network status (base case) and possible network contingencies (security constraint analysis). The task responsible will address this KPI through a comprehensive methodology that includes benchmarking, validation against reference datasets, and coordination with demonstration and evaluation activities.

The KPI was originally named “ ≥ 5 operational manoeuvres proposed by the AI artefact” but has been rephrased to better reflect the type of “operational manoeuvres” expected.

The KPI is defined as the measurable performance in system operation achieved by the AI artefact used to solve Optimal Power Flow under security constraints. The performance evaluation includes analysis of computational time, algorithm convergence, controllable-devices setpoint optimization, and remedial action performance compared to current operator-based methods.

Methodology and Evaluation Criteria

To assess the effectiveness and performance of the artificial intelligence (AI) artefact in proposing operational remedial recommendations, REE has defined four key metrics. These metrics are designed to evaluate both the computational and operational performance of the AI-generated solutions, thereby validating the artefact’s capability to support decision-making in complex grid environments.

Plan to Achieve the KPIs

To ensure the successful fulfilment of the defined metrics, REE will implement a structured evaluation and validation plan based on current operational practices and system performance. Each metric will be addressed through a dedicated methodology, supported by reference data and clear evaluation criteria.

- *Metric 5.4.1 – Computational Time*

Methodology: The algorithm will be benchmarked by executing it across a representative set of operational scenarios, including both normal and stressed grid conditions.

Measurement: Execution time will be recorded for each case, and statistical indicators such as average, minimum, and maximum times will be calculated.

Evaluation Criteria: The algorithm will be considered compliant if the computational time remains within the acceptable threshold of ≤ 5 minutes.

Reference Data: Based on current system operation logs and simulation runtimes under similar conditions.

- *Metric 5.4.2 – Algorithm Convergence*

Methodology: A large number of simulations will be conducted under varying grid conditions and initial parameters to test the algorithm's robustness.

Measurement: The number of successful convergences versus failures will be tracked, and convergence rates will be computed.

Evaluation Criteria: A convergence rate above 75% will be targeted. Failure cases will be analysed to identify algorithmic limitations and potential improvements.

Reference Data: Derived from current operational simulations and contingency analysis results.

- *Metric 5.4.3 – Power Exchange Optimization*

Methodology: The HVDC setpoints and control modes generated by the AI algorithm will be compared against those obtained through traditional operator-based methods.

Measurement: Metrics such as deviation from optimal setpoints, efficiency gains, and system stability indicators will be used.

Evaluation Criteria: the power flow capacity transmission increase will be assessed. Improvement above 5% in power flow capacity will be evaluated as a positive metric.

Reference Data: Based on historical HVDC configurations and operator-defined control strategies.

- *Metric 5.4.4 – Remedial Actions Performance*

Methodology: Contingency scenarios will be simulated, and the remedial actions proposed by the AI artefact will be compared with those currently implemented by operators.

Measurement: Effectiveness, speed of response, and impact on system reliability and stability will be evaluated.

Evaluation Criteria: The AI artifact must demonstrate its potential to enhance decision-making and reduce operational risks. Increase of power transmission capacity and associated costs reduction will be evaluated.

Reference Data: Based on existing remedial action plans, incident reports, and operator logs.

Reference Data Sources

The evaluation of all metrics will be grounded in a robust set of reference data derived from current operational practices and validated system analyses. These sources provide the necessary baseline to assess the performance and added value of the AI-based solution in realistic grid conditions.

The source datasets include:

- Historical records of operator decisions.
- SCADA logs.
- Operational records.
- Results from current Optimal Power Flow (OPF) calculations.
- Results from Security-Constrained (SC) operation analyses.

The following references will be used:

- HVDC setpoints and control modes currently defined by operators, including active/reactive power setpoints, control strategies, and operational constraints.

These reference datasets—comprising both operator decisions and outputs from current OPF and SC analyses—will serve as the baseline for comparing the performance of the AI artefact.

KPI 6.1: $\geq 30\%$ increase of oscillations detected

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservices developed by SINTEF and IEN during WP2 called “Detection of Power Oscillations” and implemented on the InterSCADA platform during WP3.

This KPI will be evaluated by comparing the performance of the deployed microservices with the technologies currently available in IPTO’s control centre.

The plan is to first use data from the real demonstrator period. If necessary, historical data provided by IPTO—related to the demonstrator and collected prior to its official start—will also be used.

KPI 6.2: $\geq 20\%$ increase of detected voltage instabilities

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservice developed by SINTEF during WP2 called “Detection of Overvoltages” and implemented on the InterSCADA platform during WP3.

This KPI will be evaluated using the observed performance of the microservice during the real demonstrator period (WP5)

The performance will be evaluated considering aspects like precision in location and speed of voltage instabilities detection. The performance will be compared by the observed by the legacy systems available in IPTO’s control centre.

KPI 6.3: $\geq 20\%$ increase in the accuracy of detected RoCoFs

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservice developed by RWTH able to calculate ROCOF values during dynamic conditions, as per defined by the IEC/IEEE 60255-118-1:2018.

This KPI will be evaluated using the observed performance of the microservice using real demonstrator data and simulations of dynamic events. The performance will be compared with the ROCOF values calculated by traditional algorithms available in the field.

KPI 6.4: $\geq 40\%$ increase of detected system splits

This KPI is directly associated with the modular microservice developed by SINTEF during WP2 called “System split monitoring” and implemented on the InterSCADA platform during WP3.

This KPI will be evaluated using data from the real demonstrator period. If it is necessary, historical data provided by IPTO can be used. As the last option, simulated data could be used.

The performance will be evaluated considering aspects like precision in split location and speed of split detection. The performance will be compared to outputs obtained from the legacy systems available in IPTO’s control centre.

KPI 6.5: ≥ 15 Synchronized DC Measurement Units (DMUs) and Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) installed and integrated in the metering systems.

Demo 1:

At least 3 PMUs will be integrated for each of AC part of the pilot (For ASM substation, one for SCOV substation and one for AC critical Load).

1 DMU for 700 DC bus. It will be integrated into the InterSCADA and our developed Microservices.

Demo 2:

18 PMU measurements will be integrated into the InterSCADA platform, obtaining that data from a legacy PDC. (Responsible of the integration: IPTO and CIRCE)

KPI 7.1: 10 adaptation requirements for grid codes

This KPI will assess the number of proposed adaptations to regulations identified within the regulatory analysis performed under InterSCADA project. Thus, its success will be evaluated by quantifying the proposed adaptations developed within Task 6.1 “*Recommendations to enhance and extend existing grid codes and standards*” and later included in the deliverable D6.1 “*Recommendations to existing grid codes and amendments in the standards*” and comparing with the established project goal.

KPI 7.2: 15 techno-economic parameters assessed, associated with InterSCADA solutions

Within this KPI techno-economic factors of solutions developed and proposed by InterSCADA project will be evaluated. The main groups of factors are the following:

1. Factors associated with SCADA systems
2. Factors associated with PMU devices
3. Factors associated with overall power system stability
4. Factors associated with hybrid AC/DC power systems

Each parameter will address such criteria as:

- influence on cost of implementation and cost of operation as compared with the common available solutions
- influence on saved cost resulting from energy loss, unsupplied energy, unprovided services, etc. as compared with the common available solutions
- technical or other types (e.g. organizational) of barriers in implementation and their resulting cost

Data for calculation of individual parameters will be collected within Task 6.3 from all possible sources, including TSOs, DSOs, software and hardware developers in the consortium, advisory board and associated partners. The precise list of at least 15 indicators as well as criteria for each will be the subject of Task 6.3.

KPI 7.3: 10% energy system cost reduction

This KPI will evaluate areas of power system functioning, including operation, maintenance, investments etc. in which InterSCADA solutions could contribute to a reduction of cost, aiming for 10% reduction as compared with general, of-the-shelf solutions and current practices. Since obtaining information on the real costs of these items might be impossible in many cases, and the prices themselves can be highly

dynamic, the reduction can also be expressed in other units, such as MWh, per unit, seconds, etc.

Collection of input data as well as necessary calculations will be performed in Task 6.3.

KPI 8.1: 10 key organizations actively engaged (via dissemination synergies & knowledge exchange)

This KPI measures the success on the engagement activities focused on external stakeholders (in this case, engaged organizations) participation. It will count the number of key organizations which actively participate in the different engagement campaigns organized under WP7 “*Dissemination and communication*” lead by ICONS and coordinated with all partners. Such activities will take as basis the communication and dissemination strategic plan and will be documented as well.

The original title of this KPI referred to “associations”. This word was changed to “organizations” to better reflect the type of associations intended to be reached.

KPI 8.2: 50 direct contacts of potentially interested users, investors, enablers

ICONS will facilitate the collection of contacts and descriptions of potentially interested end users and investors will support the WP6 involved partners. All partners, especially the partners involved, and task leads in WP6 will actively participate in mapping of the investors and interested end users ICONS will keep in mind this KPI and encourage the partners for active interaction. ICONS will recommend the application of relevant communication means; however, ICONS will NOT contact personally the interested investors and end users it will be the responsibility of respective partners. The strong collaboration with WP6 will guarantee the achievement of the KPI.

KPI 8.3: 5 new work items as contributions (evolution/adaptation) of standards.

This KPI quantifies the amount of “work items” contributed by InterSCADA for adaptation improvements of technical norms. Such items stand for developed recommendations presented by InterSCADA (as European project) within open consultations, or discussions with European bodies. The success of this KPI will be assessed by contrasting the number of items developed against the initial target of 5.

5. Demo 1 Specifications

5.1. Description of the demo

The power grid of Terni serves a city and some villages for a total of about 100,000 inhabitants. The substations are distributed on the territory of the Municipality of Terni following the concentration of homes, businesses, and enterprises on criteria related to consumption and production of energy, which is mainly from PV power plants (Figure 1).

Figure 1: User and power plant distribution in Terni

The Italian demo uses a large portion of the AC distribution grid to host the new 700VDC unipolar distribution section. The main DC components are two LV AC/DC converters to power the DC bus-bar (Figure 2). The DC distribution includes a storage system, a PV power plant, an electric vehicle (EV) charging station, and a power distribution for priority loads.

The ongoing transformation of distribution networks requires a shift toward smarter, more flexible infrastructure that can support the evolving nature of energy generation and consumption. In the Italian demo led by ASM Terni, a hybrid AC/DC system is being implemented and tested in a real-world low-voltage (LV) distribution grid. This hybrid approach marks a significant innovation in grid architecture, designed to enhance efficiency, reduce conversion losses, and better accommodate the growing presence of RES, energy storage systems, and EV charging infrastructure.

Figure 2: Overview diagram of the Italian demo

Figure 3: Overview of hybrid AC/DC system in Italy

In response to the increasing complexity of modern distribution networks, the Terni demo addresses the operational challenges posed by high penetration of inverter-based DERs in LV grids. As LV systems evolve from passive infrastructures to active, bidirectional energy environments driven by widespread adoption of RES, storage systems, and electric mobility enhanced grid observability and controllability become essential. The first part of the demo focuses on the implementation of AMI for real time monitoring of the LV grid, integrated with coordinated control of inverter-based DERs via the SCADA platform. By combining high resolution field data acquisition with intelligent control, the system enables functionalities such as voltage regulation, demand response, and mitigation of reverse power flow at the secondary substation level. This approach supports a scalable and interoperable pathway to modernizing traditional distribution networks, enhancing their resilience, flexibility, and readiness for hybrid AC/DC operation.

However, while multiple data collection systems are already operational in the demo (AMI smart meters at the LV level, PMUs for dynamic AC measurements, and DC side telemetry via Eaton’s local microgrid controller), these remain isolated from one another. To extract real operational value, InterSCADA is required to act as the unifying monitoring layer that interfaces with all these sources and ensures synchronized, real-time visibility of the full network. This includes AC feeders, DC bus conditions, power exchange through the two Smart Grid Converters (AFEs) battery state of charge, PV output, EV charging profiles, and even MV substation information. One core objective of this demo is thus to guarantee that InterSCADA becomes the single platform capable of receiving, time aligning, and visualizing all available measurements across the hybrid grid enabling smarter system management and serving as the backbone for downstream automation and control services.

Building upon the unified monitoring framework described previously, the next part of the demo focuses on enhancing the controllability of power flow in the Terni hybrid AC/DC grid through the coordinated adjustment of droop control parameters on the two AFE converters. These converters AIT Smart Grid Converters (ASGCs) are positioned at the interface between the AC substations (ASM and SCOV) and the central 700 VDC unipolar bus. Leveraging real time voltage, current, and power measurements collected from across the AC and DC subsystems (e.g., PMUs, smart meters, battery systems, EV chargers, and the PV plant), the InterSCADA platform evaluates the system’s load and generation profile. Based on this evaluation, it dynamically computes and dispatches updated droop coefficients to the AFEs, allowing for active redistribution of power flows. This ensures that both converters share the DC load proportionally and adaptively, enhancing redundancy, voltage stability, and operational resilience.

The implementation of this functionality enables automated coordination between the two secondary substations, facilitating optimized bidirectional power exchange and load balancing across the hybrid grid. By fine tuning droop slopes in real time, the system mitigates risks such as current oscillations, voltage deviations, and overloading of individual feeders. This functionality is critical in hybrid networks where energy sources and loads are highly dynamic and geographically dispersed. Control commands are securely transmitted via InterSCADA using standardized protocols, and the adjustment process is designed to occur without disrupting ongoing AFE operation. As a result, this part of the demo represents a key step toward advanced grid-forming behavior, enabling decentralized yet coordinated converter control and paving the way for more flexible, reliable, and DER-integrated low-voltage distribution systems.

5.1.1. Name of demo

<i>Demo identification</i>	
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name of demo</i>
	AMI-based LV grid monitoring and inverter-based DER control integration in SCADA

5.1.2. Scope and objectives of demo

<i>Scope and objectives of demo</i>

Co-Funded by the European Union

Scope	This demo encompasses both the real-time monitoring and intelligent control functionalities required to manage a hybrid AC/DC low voltage distribution network with high penetration of inverter-based DER. The first part focuses on integrating Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), power electronic converters, and distributed sensors into the InterSCADA platform to unify data collection from various AC and DC grid segments, enabling full situational awareness and Sharing data with legacy system SCADA. The second part focuses on demonstrating redistributing substation power flows so that they share the DC load proportionally and adaptively, improving redundancy, voltage stability, and operational resilience.
Objective(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-Time LV Grid Monitoring: Utilize AMI and standardized communication protocols (e.g., Modbus, MQTT, IEC 61850, etc.) to monitor voltage, current, and consumption patterns in real time inside the pilot. • Among the objectives to be achieved, a key priority is to establish effective methods for exchanging information with legacy SCADA systems. Specifically, it is essential to ensure the ability to send measurements from all devices included in the pilot to the legacy systems, and, conversely, to receive from these systems the set-points and commands to be transmitted to the same devices • Enable real-time power flow monitoring and control between secondary substations in a hybrid AC/DC grid using the InterSCADA platform. • Dynamically adjust the droop coefficients of AFE converters based on real-time grid measurements to ensure balanced load sharing and stable operation. • Improve operational resilience by enabling autonomous local control of converters during disturbances or partial communication loss. • Enhance the flexibility and responsiveness of the LV network by supporting seamless power exchange and redundancy through coordinated AFE control
Short description	<p>The first part aims to expand traditional SCADA capabilities by combining AMI-based monitoring with active inverter control. Through InterSCADA, we aim to achieve real-time supervision, dynamic DER management, and seamless interaction between smart devices, customers, and legacy infrastructure, significantly improving grid reliability and flexibility.</p> <p>Next, building upon the unified monitoring framework described above, the second part of the demo focuses on enhancing the controllability of power flow in the Terni hybrid AC/DC grid through the coordinated adjustment of droop control parameters on the two AFE converters. These converters AIT Smart Grid Converters (ASGCs) are positioned at the interface between the AC substations (ASM and SCOV) and the central 700 VDC unipolar bus. Leveraging real time voltage, current, and power measurements collected from across the AC and DC subsystems, the InterSCADA platform evaluates the system's load and generation profile. Based on this evaluation, it dynamically computes and dispatches updated droop coefficients to the AFEs, allowing for active redistribution of power flows. This ensures that both converters share the DC load proportionally and adaptively, enhancing redundancy, voltage stability, and operational resilience.</p>
Complete description	<p>The first part of the demo highlights the need for integration between control and monitoring systems for electricity generation and those in place within distribution networks. This integration can be achieved through the use of an open-source SCADA system, which enables the exchange and distribution of data across the different levels of the electricity value chain from generation to distribution.</p> <p>The information generated by this system is also shared with legacy SCADA systems, which are traditionally used for controlling generation and distribution infrastructure, in order to ensure operational continuity and compatibility with existing architectures.</p> <p>This integration makes it possible to optimize the use of renewable energy sources and enhance monitoring capabilities, thereby contributing to the stability of low-voltage networks. With the increasing penetration of distributed renewable generation, a significant share of energy is produced by end-user inverters. Only through effective information sharing can grid stability be ensured, enabling optimized voltage regulation, frequency stability, and load balancing through real-time data and automated control mechanisms.</p>

	<p>The goal of this approach is to provide grid operators with advanced tools to increase network resilience, reduce energy losses, and enable higher hosting capacity for renewable sources without compromising reliability.</p> <p>To fully achieve real-time monitoring and control in our LV hybrid AC/DC grid, the InterSCADA platform must integrate various data sources AMI, PMUs, inverters, storage through multi-protocol support including Modbus. In the pilot project, PMUs and DMUs play a crucial role in achieving full grid observability, with their data integrated into the Interscada system to enable comprehensive monitoring and seamless data sharing. Their deployment improves predictive modelling, protection, regulation, and load balancing, ultimately strengthening grid resilience and stability—especially important in grids with high renewable energy penetration.</p> <p>The second part of the demo is focused on dynamic regulation of the hybrid AC/DC grid in Terni, the development and integration of an intelligent automatic algorithm within the InterSCADA platform is proposed. The goal is to optimize, in real time, the droop control coefficients (drop factors) of the AFE converters.</p> <p>Based on the unified monitoring framework described earlier, the algorithm receives real-time measurements of voltage, current, and power from both the AC and DC subsystems. By continuously analysing the system’s load and generation profile, the algorithm detects any power imbalance between the two AFE converters (ASGC) and dynamically computes optimal updated droop factor values, which are then automatically transmitted to the converters.</p> <p>This adaptive regulation enables an efficient and proportional sharing of the DC load between the two AFE units, enhancing operational redundancy, voltage stability on the 700 VDC bus, and the resilience of the system under variable load conditions or disturbances.</p> <p>The ultimate goal is to ensure autonomous, coordinated, and optimized management of power flows in the hybrid grid, minimizing the need for manual intervention and improving overall system performance</p>
<p>Related case(s) business</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing information between generation and distribution systems • Optimizing the use of energy from RES • Improving grid reliability and stability • Monitoring parameters for fault detection and response • Enhance grid resilience in the face of variable loads and renewable generation. • Improve asset utilization, especially converters and control infrastructure.

5.1.3. Key performance indicators (KPI)

Key performance indicators			
ID	Name	Description	Reference to mentioned demo objectives
KPI_01	Real-time Data Acquisition Rate	Percentage of data successfully collected from AMI and monitoring devices in real time (e.g., every 10 minute or less). The target value is $\geq 98\%$.	Real-time LV grid monitoring
KPI_02	Data Exchange Success Rate	Successful data exchanges (both measurements sent, and commands received) between the pilot and legacy SCADA systems. The target value is $\geq 95\%$ successful data exchange.	Integration with legacy SCADA systems
KPI_03	Command Execution Accuracy	Value of set-points or commands transmitted from SCADA that are correctly executed by the pilot’s devices. The target value is ≤ 200 ms assessed by average execution latency. Max latency is ≤ 500 ms.	Integration with legacy SCADA systems
KPI_04	Interoperability Compliance	Percentage of successfully validated communications using standardized protocols (Modbus, MQTT, IEC	Use of standard protocols in real-time monitoring

		61850). The target value is $\geq 98\%$ successful communication sessions using standard protocols	
KPI_05	Droop Coefficient Update Time	Time (in seconds) taken by InterSCADA to detect imbalance and send updated droop settings to converters. The target is a total update time (detection + dispatch) ≤ 30 sec. Update system stabilization time: System stabilizes e.g. in one minute.	Dynamically adjust droop coefficients based on real-time measurements
KPI_06	Power Flow Adjustment Time	Time taken to stabilize power flows after a disturbance or load variation. Total time to reach power flow stability ≤ 1 minute.	Integration with legacy SCADA systems

5.1.4. Use case conditions

<i>Demo conditions</i>
<i>Assumptions</i>
It is assumed that the existing AVEVA SCADA system is operational and configured to monitor key pilot devices.
<i>Prerequisites</i>
Smart meters, sensors, and PMUs/DMUs must be installed, functional, and capable of sending data to SCADA and InterSCADA systems.
<i>Demo conditions</i>
<i>Assumptions</i>
All involved systems and devices (SCADA, InterSCADA, sensors, DERs) support Modbus (TCP/RTU), MQTT, and/or API-based communication.
<i>Prerequisites</i>
Modbus, MQTT, and API drivers inside InterSCADA microservices must be tested and active for real-time data acquisition and control signal dispatch

5.2. Diagrams of demo

Figure 4: Monitoring and control architecture in Demo 1

The DC microgrid control architecture implemented in the Terni demo is based on a hierarchical and distributed control strategy designed for real-time energy management and power flow optimization. The system relies on a robust communication network using TCP/IP over Ethernet and the Modbus protocol for seamless integration of industrial controllers and power electronics devices. Local controllers installed on each controllable asset (such as PV systems, battery storage, EV chargers, and AFE converters) execute primary and secondary control functions, including current regulation, droop-based power sharing, SoC-dependent rules, and MPPT for solar inverters. These controllers collect and transmit operational data to a central controller, which manages energy coordination, visualization, and storage via a dedicated SCADA interface and database. The DC grid central control also communicates with the AC grid platform to enable coordinated AC/DC power exchange and future demand-response functionalities, forming the foundation for seamless hybrid grid management at the demo site.

At the core of the setup, a set of distributed microservices runs on a Linux-based central controller, responsible for acquiring real-time measurements and managing control actions across various demo devices, including PV systems, batteries, vehicle-to-grid converters, and AC/DC loads. These devices communicate through Modbus TCP or Modbus RTU protocols. The InterSCADA platform plays a central role by acting as a middleware layer that interfaces directly with the legacy SCADA system to enable bi-directional data exchange. Through MQTT, InterSCADA synchronizes and aggregates all incoming field data, ensuring coherent and timely system observability. Additionally, InterSCADA can send control commands and setpoints directly to demo devices, enabling autonomous operation and advanced services. This architecture supports full visibility and coordination between the legacy SCADA infrastructure and the modern microgrid components, aligning with the objectives of Task 3.4 to enhance real-time monitoring and control at the demo level

1. Collected from field devices (AFE, PV, Battery, EV, etc.)
Sent via MODBUS TCP/RTU to Microservices
Forwarded to InterSCADA for processing and visualization
2. Measurements (voltage, current, power) / Control Commands / Setpoints Issued by InterSCADA (based on logic/AI/microservices)
3. SCADA and InterSCADA Synchronization Achieved via MODBUS TCP and MQTT Enables two-way communication for status updates, alarms, and commands

Figure 5: Control center overview

Algorithm module description (InterSCADA hybrid AC/DC demo)

In the hybrid AC/DC demo, the Central controller is replaced by a modular and service-oriented architecture built around InterSCADA microservices. These microservices serve as the core intelligence of the platform, managing real-time monitoring and control functions across the entire grid. Key field devices including the two AFE converters, ZekaLabs sensors, battery storage systems, and V2G chargers continuously transmit measurement data such as voltage, current, state of charge, and power flows using the Modbus TCP/IP protocol. This raw data is collected and translated into standardized JSON formats by a protocol translation layer and published to an internal MQTT broker, allowing secure and scalable data exchange across the system.

Once the data is published, the InterSCADA platform performs real-time state estimation to analyse the current operational conditions of the grid, including the AC and DC subsystems. Based on this analysis, advanced control algorithms dynamically calculate updated droop parameters and power setpoints for the AFE converters. These commands are then securely communicated back to the devices via Modbus, enabling fine-tuned regulation of power flow, load balancing, and voltage stabilization across the hybrid grid. By leveraging this distributed microservice approach, InterSCADA enables adaptive and resilient grid management, ensuring real-time responsiveness to fluctuations in generation, load, and system topology without relying on a single centralized controller.

5.3. Technical details

5.3.1. Actors

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Monitoring (AMI + DER data integration)		This group consists of devices that collect real-time electrical parameters such as voltage, current, power quality, and consumption data. These measurements are essential for monitoring grid stability and detecting anomalies.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
InterSCADA platform	System platform	Acting as a middleware layer that interfaces with the legacy SCADA system, ensuring the synchronization and integration of real-time monitoring data from all grid sections. This enables unified observability and paves the way for advanced control functionalities across the hybrid grid.	
Smart Meter (AMI Unit)	Device	Measures real-time electricity consumption, voltage levels, and power quality at customer premises. Transmits data to the SCADA system via AMI.	
PMUs	Sensor	Time-synchronized phasor measurements for voltage/current in the LV grid.	
DMU	Sensor		
Local Controller (SMP 4/DP)	Linux Controllers	Collects measurements from field devices (meters, sensors, converters, etc.) and communicates with legacy SCADA and InterSCADA.	Data is collected from: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AFE1 and AFE2 (ASGCs) 2. Zekalabs DC/DC converter (connected to PV, battery, DC EV charger) 3. GFC inverter for critical AC loads 4. EV charger controller 5. BMS (battery management system)
Central legacy SCADA system	System	Receives and aggregates AMI and DER data, enables visualization (GUI) and data logging.	
Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Actuators and control devices		This group includes the power electronic converters and local control devices capable of adjusting power flow, setting droop parameters, or controlling voltage. They respond to control commands from SCADA or InterSCADA systems.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
AFE Converter (ASGC)	Power Converter	Interfaces AC and DC subsystems, supports bidirectional flow and droop control.	

Zekalabs Converter	Power Converter(Device)	Controls battery and PV operation, includes MPPT and SoC-based behaviour.	
Grid-Forming Inverter	Device	Ensures voltage formation and stability for critical AC loads in islanded operation	

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
communication interfaces		This group includes microservices, local controllers, and communication protocols (MODBUS TCP/IP and RTU) responsible for coordinating data exchange between field devices and supervisory systems. These components form the backbone of real-time interaction and synchronization between SCADA, InterSCADA, and edge equipment.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Microservices	Software	Deployed on Linux controller; manages field device data (via MODBUS TCP/RTU) and control logic. Routes data to/from SCADA and InterSCADA.	
MODBUS TCP/IP	Protocol	Used to connect higher-level systems (SCADA, InterSCADA) with controllers and AFE units. Enables fast bidirectional communication.	
MODBUS RTU	Protocol	Serial protocol used to connect to DC converters (e.g., battery)	

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
System operator		The key stakeholders responsible for monitoring, managing, and operating the grid.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Grid Operator (DSO-)	Human	Person responsible for operating and maintaining the distribution	Monitors grid conditions via SCADA, analyses data, and takes control actions to ensure stability.
End-User (Customer/Prosumer)	Human	Electricity consumer who may also produce energy via PV systems or batteries (prosumer)	Consumes electricity and may also generate power (prosumer). Participates in demand response programs via AMI.
SCADA Engineer	Human	Technical specialist responsible for configuring, updating, and managing the SCADA system infrastructure.	Configures and maintains the SCADA system, ensuring proper communication and data processing.
Energy Market Operator	Human	Person or institution responsible for managing energy and ancillary service markets.	Manages ancillary service markets, enabling DERs to participate in grid services.

5.4. Step by step analysis of demo

5.4.1. Overview of use cases

<i>Use case conditions</i>		
No.		
01	Use case name	Send Measurement Data from AMI to SCADA
	Use case description	Smart meters and sensors collect voltage, current, and power values from AC/DC nodes in real-time and send them to InterSCADA via Modbus and MQTT protocols
	Primary actor	Smart Meter / Sensor
	Triggering event	Data sampling at defined interval
	Pre-condition	AMI devices are installed and configured; communication drivers (Modbus/MQTT) are active
	Post-condition	Data successfully received and stored in InterSCADA, ready for visualization and analytics
02	Use case name	Share Data with Legacy SCADA
	Use case description	InterSCADA shares measurement data with the legacy SCADA (AVEVA System Platform) via a dedicated microservice-based API driver.
	Primary actor	InterSCADA Microservice
	Triggering event	Data processed in InterSCADA
	Pre-condition	Legacy SCADA endpoint is reachable; microservice driver for API is operational
	Post-condition	Legacy SCADA receives up-to-date data from InterSCADA
03	Use case name	Receive Control Set-point from SCADA
	Use case description	Legacy SCADA sends updated control commands or set-points to InterSCADA to be transmitted to the hybrid AC/DC pilot devices (e.g., converter setpoints).
	Primary actor	Legacy SCADA
	Triggering event	Operator sends control signal
	Pre-condition	Control API interface is operational and devices are in communication state
	Post-condition	Control command received by pilot device (e.g., converter) and executed
04	Use case name	Share PMU/DMU data to InterSCADA
	Use case description	PMU/DMU units transmit high-resolution data (synchrophasors, DC voltages) through Modbus or MQTT to the InterSCADA platform for real-time monitoring and grid analysis.
	Primary actor	PMU/DMU Device
	Triggering event	Time-synchronized data sampling
	Pre-condition	PMUs and DMUs are deployed and configured; communication path to InterSCADA is active
	Post-condition	Synchronized data is integrated into InterSCADA and used for grid visibility and stability tools
05	Use case name	Microservice Data Distribution
	Use case description	Internal microservice memory shares acquired data between different communication modules (e.g., MQTT broker, API server) to ensure multi-channel availability of data
	Primary actor	InterSCADA Microservice
	Triggering event	New data sample stored in memory
	Pre-condition	Memory buffer inside microservice is active and accessible by drivers
	Post-condition	Data becomes available simultaneously for API and MQTT consumers
06	Use case name	Real-Time Droop Control for AFE Power Sharing

<i>Use case conditions</i>	
No.	
	<p>Use case description</p> <p>To ensure voltage stability and proper power sharing in the DC microgrid, InterSCADA microservices operate in real time by continuously interacting with key field devices such as AFEs, battery converters, and ZekaLabs sensors Each microservice includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A communication module that gathers real-time measurements (e.g., voltage, current, power flow, SoC) from devices using Modbus TCP/IP or Modbus RTU protocols (especially in ZekaLabs). - A monitoring module that evaluates grid status, such as voltage deviations or imbalances, based on the collected data.
	<p>Primary actor</p> <p>InterSCADA Microservice Layer</p>
	<p>Triggering event</p> <p>Change in DC grid condition (e.g., load variation or renewable generation shift) leading to deviation from nominal 700 V</p>
	<p>Pre-condition</p> <p>AFEs, battery storage, PV inverters, and ZekaLabs sensors are operational and provide real-time data via Modbus to MQTT.</p> <p>InterSCADA microservices are subscribed to relevant MQTT topics and actively process incoming measurements.</p>
	<p>Post-condition</p> <p>Updated control setpoints are transmitted to the relevant devices.</p> <p>Power sharing is balanced.</p> <p>DC voltage is restored close to nominal.</p>

5.4.2. Steps – Use cases

5.4.2.1. Use case #1

Use case #1 description

Real-time monitoring and control via AMI in LV Hybrid AC/DC Grid
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Use case step by step analysis

<i>Use case</i>								
<i>Use case name</i>	Real-time monitoring and control via AMI in LV Hybrid AC/DC Grid							
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Smart meter and sensor collect data	Real-time measurement	Voltage, current, and power values are measured from AC and DC nodes	REPORT	Smart meters / Sensors	Linux Central Controller	I-01	
02	Legacy SCADA receives update	Legacy integration	InterSCADA communicates with Legacy SCADA via Modbus TCP	POST	InterSCADA	Legacy SCADA	I-02	

Use case								
Use case name		Real-time monitoring and control via AMI in LV Hybrid AC/DC Grid						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
03	DER controllers receive command	Control dispatch	Commands (e.g., curtailment, setpoints) are sent from SCADA to inverters via microservices	WRITE	Legacy SCADA / InterSCADA	AIT AFEs, Zekalabs Converters	I-03	
04	Feedback loop	Response monitoring	DER units confirm execution and send operational feedback	REPORT	DER Controllers	InterSCADA Platform	I-04	

5.4.2.2. Use case #2

Use case #2 description

Share Data with Legacy SCADA

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Share Data with Legacy SCADA						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Processed data available	InterSCADA data aggregation	InterSCADA receives and processes real-time data from meters, sensors, and controllers	PROCESS	InterSCADA Platform	InterSCADA Microservice	I-01	
02	Microservice triggers export	API-based data push	A dedicated microservice prepares and exports the required data to legacy SCADA	TRANSMIT	InterSCADA Microservice	Legacy SCADA (AVEVA System Platform)	I-02	
03	Legacy SCADA receives update	API communication successful	Legacy SCADA successfully receives and stores updated measurements	RECEIVE	InterSCADA Microservice	Legacy SCADA (AVEVA System Platform)	I-03	

5.4.2.3. Use case #3

Use case #3 description

Receive Control Set-point from SCADA

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name Receive Control Set-point from SCADA								
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Legacy SCADA sends control set-point	SCADA issues command	Legacy SCADA sends a control set-point (e.g., power limit, voltage reference) to a device via InterSCADA.	POST	Legacy SCADA	InterSCADA	I-01	
02	InterSCADA processes command	Command parsing	InterSCADA microservice receives, validates, and translates the control set-point into a format suitable for the target device.	PROCESS	InterSCADA	InterSCADA Microservice	I-02	
03	Command transmitted to device	Command dispatch	The control command is sent to the target converter (e.g., AFE, DC/DC) via supported protocol (Modbus RTU, MQTT).	SEND	InterSCADA Microservice	Power electronic converter	I-03	

5.4.2.4. Use case #4

Use case #4 description

Share PMU/DMU Data to InterSCADA

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Share PMU/DMU Data to InterSCADA						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	PMU/DMU is operational	Time-synchronized data sampling	The PMU/DMU device performs continuous measurements of voltage, current, and synchrophasors in real-time..	GET	PMU/DMU device	InterSCADA	I-01	
02	Communication link is active	Data transmission	The device sends the synchronized data to InterSCADA using either Modbus or MQTT protocol.	PUSH	PMU/DMU device	InterSCADA	I-02	
03	InterSCADA receives data	Data integration and analysis	InterSCADA stores and processes the received PMU/DMU data for real-time visualization and grid stability tools. .	PROCESS	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	I-03	

5.4.2.5. Use case #5

Use case #5 description

Microservice Data Distribution

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Microservice Data Distribution						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Data received by microservice	Internal memory update	Measurement data from field devices is stored in the internal memory of the microservice.	STORE	Communication Driver (Modbus/MQTT)	Microservice Memory	I-01	
02	Microservice needs to distribute	Inter-module data sharing	Internal memory shares data with different modules such as MQTT	PUSH	Microservice Memory	MQTT Module / API Module	I-02	

Use case								
Use case name		Microservice Data Distribution						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
			Broker and API Server.					
03	InterSCADA receives data	Data integration and analysis	InterSCADA stores and processes the received PMU/DMU data for real-time visualization and grid stability tools. .	PROCESS	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	I-03	

5.4.2.6. Use case #6

Use case #6 description

Real-Time Droop Control for AFE Power Sharing

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Real-Time Droop Control for AFE Power Sharing						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Grid condition monitored	Real-time measurement acquisition	InterSCADA collects voltage, current, and power data from both AFE converters (ASM & SCOV) via the central controller.	GET	InterSCADA	AFE 1 (ASM), AFE 2 (SCOV)	InterSCADA platform	
02	Measurement received	Power flow analysis	InterSCADA processes input data to determine any power imbalance or droop deviation between converters.	ANALYZE	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	
03	Control action issued	Droop coefficient update	InterSCADA sends updated droop settings to AFE 1 and AFE 2 via the Linux controller.	SET	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	InterSCADA	

Use case								
Use case name		Real-Time Droop Control for AFE Power Sharing						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
04	New settings applied	Local droop response	Each AFE adjusts its output current/power according to the new droop coefficient.	ACT	AFE 1 & AFE 2	AFE 1 & AFE 2	AFE 1 & AFE 2	

5.5. Information exchanged

Information exchanged			
Information exchanged, ID	Name of information exchanged	Description of information exchanged	Requirement, R-IDs
I-01	Real-time voltage and current from AMI	Smart meters and sensors measure voltage, current, and power in AC/DC segments and send the data periodically to InterSCADA via Modbus or MQTT	Co-Is-04
I-02	PMU synchrophasor data	PMUs send time-synchronized phasor data (voltage magnitude and angle) for grid visibility. Communication occurs over Modbus TCP or MQTT depending on deployment.	Co-Is-04
I-03	DMU DC voltage and current readings	DMUs collect high-resolution DC node data (voltages, currents) and transmit it to InterSCADA for real-time analysis and storage.	
I-04	Legacy SCADA input signal set-points	Legacy SCADA (e.g., AVEVA) sends control signals or set-points (e.g., charge limit, active power) to the Linux controller for execution via microservices.	
I-05	InterSCADA to Legacy SCADA data stream	A dedicated microservice shares processed AMI/PMU/DMU measurements to the legacy SCADA system for redundancy and operational awareness.	
I-06	Microservice internal data handoff	Measurement data is shared between internal modules (e.g., Modbus module, MQTT broker, HTTP server) to allow multipoint access and ensure integration flexibility.	

5.6. Requirements

Requirements (optional)		
Categories ID	Category name for requirements	Category description
Co-Is	Communication & Interoperability	Requirements that ensure reliable and standardized data exchange among system components.
Requirement ID	Requirement name	Requirement description
Da-Pr-01	Standard protocol usage	All devices must support standard protocols such as Modbus TCP, MQTT, or HTTP for real-time data communication.
Da-Pr-02	Multi-channel data access	Data from AMI, PMU, and DMU must be available to both InterSCADA and legacy SCADA through microservices

Da-Pr-03	Internal module data handoff	Microservices must reliably exchange data across modules (e.g., MQTT broker, Modbus module, API server).
Requirements (optional)		
Categories ID	Category name for requirements	Category description
Co-Is	Data Processing & Storage	Requirements for handling, storing, and processing grid data in real-time or for historical analysis
Requirement ID	Requirement name	Requirement description
Co-Is-01	Real-time data storage	InterSCADA must store all incoming real-time data from AMI/PMU/DMU with proper time stamps.
Co-Is-02	Timestamp synchronization	PMU and DMU data must include GPS-synchronized timestamps to ensure coherent analysis.

6. Demo 2 Specifications

6.1. Description of the demo

RES with PE interfaces and HVDC links are transforming the HETS into a hybrid AC/DC grid. It is worth mentioning that in 2024, RES contributed 55% to the electricity generation mix. Moreover, HVDC links are increasingly integrated. One example is the interconnection of mainland of Greece with the island of Crete that consists of a HVDC link with voltage-source converter (VSC) technology, as well as HVAC interconnections. Therefore, this interconnection to the HETS will be hybrid as it will consist of HVDC in parallel to HVAC, i.e. the HVDC link will be embedded in the HETS under normal operating conditions. Similarly, the Dodecanese interconnection will include a HVDC link with VSC technology, between Corinth (part of HETS) and the island of Kos (currently part of a Non-Interconnected Island, NII), as well as HVAC interconnections of the NIIs of the Dodecanese region between each other and the HETS. The two above mentioned HVDC links are depicted with yellow dotted lines in Figure 6. Another HVDC interconnection, the GRITA, interconnects the South Italy with Greece, ensuring the access to EU grid by new energy producers such as Greece, Albania and Turkey and is considered a significant contribution to the Mediterranean ring reinforcement, fostering the East-West electrical energy exchanges. This HVDC link, which is the main focus of Demo 2, is shown with a yellow solid line in Figure 6.

This demo aims to showcase the benefits of having a WAMPAC system processing the information of an AC/DC hybrid grid in real-time, enabling the optimal operation of the grid and supporting the security analyses by bridging a crucial gap. Local protections and controls, despite their rapid response time in the hundreds of milliseconds range, are limited to a single substation. This category also includes reactive compensation devices, Flexible AC Transmission System (FACTS) devices and tap changers. Conversely, traditional SCADAs are able to present information regarding breaker positions, power flows, and voltage and current values. However, they operate at a slow pace, e.g., in the order of several seconds, with the information serving as a reference, while control operations are executed manually by the operators in the dispatch centre. The proposed InterSCADA platform aims to fill the gap between the two existing solutions (i.e., local protections and controls, and conventional SCADA), since they are able to protect and control a wide area with a significantly faster reaction time, which can be kept extremely low, accounting for inevitable communication and processing delays. The proposed system aims to provide an additional point of view and analysis of the power grid that cannot be obtained with the current tools and tackle the challenges imposed by the increasing integration of hybrid AC/DC systems.

Figure 6: PMU locations in the HETS

6.1.1. Name of demo

Demo identification	
ID	Name of demo
	Implementing WAMPAC algorithms for AC/DC hybrid power systems

6.1.2. Scope and objectives of demo

Scope and objectives of demo	
Scope	Technologies such as HVDC-links, will play a major role in the future transmission system operation. The integration of HVDC systems introduces new fast dynamics to the power grid. In this context, WAMPAC systems are considered as a promising technology to improve grid observability and enhance the overall stability of power systems. WAMPAC systems rely on data obtained from PMUs deployed at suitable points, capturing accurate and time-synchronized information about the state and the dynamics of the power grid. The main scope of this demo is to test the services that will be developed within the InterSCADA platform (e.g., detection of overvoltages, power oscillations monitoring, detection of critical changes in frequency, etc.), using PMUs data from the field to showcase the capabilities of the next generation of power system monitoring and control systems, especially for hybrid AC/DC systems.
Objective(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve grid observability: one goal of this demo is to track critical fast system dynamics in real time by using PMUs that the conventional SCADA system fails to capture.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the stability of power systems: by analysing and processing data from PMUs, the algorithms to be developed will facilitate accurate decision-making and stabilization measures. • Demonstrate the ability of the InterSCADA platform to process real PMU data and detect key system events. • Validate monitoring and control services in a hybrid AC/DC context. • Compare WAMPAC to conventional SCADA.
Short description	<p>Greece is interconnected with Italy with a HVDC link, known as GRITA. It is a mono-polar link with sea return utilising thyristor converters, with a rated voltage of 400 kV, a rated current of 1250 A and a rated power of 500 MW which can flow in both directions between Galatina (Italy) and Arachthos (Greece). Furthermore, 18 PMUs are installed in the HETS sending measurements to a Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC) in the dispatch centre that can provide time-synchronized information with high resolution and in particular three-phase measurements of currents and voltages (magnitude, phase), as well as frequency. A WAMPAC system processing PMU information of an AC/DC hybrid grid in near real-time could improve grid observability and enhance the stability of HETS. For this purpose, InterSCADA will provide and demonstrate advanced algorithms for (i) detection of overvoltages, (ii) detection of power oscillations, (iii) RoCoF monitoring, (iv) system split monitoring, (v) inertia assessment and (vi) fault detections, (vii) setpoints for providing ancillary services.</p>
Complete description	<p>There is an increasing concern regarding potential interactions associated with HVDC systems and other power system components. Historically, large synchronous generators have served as the backbone for providing technical capabilities. In the future, a growing amount of generation via PE will lead to a system with very low level of synchronous generation. In such systems, complex interactions could occur between HVDC systems and different controllers of the PE devices or with the synchronous generators in the electrical vicinity of HVDC converter stations.</p> <p>WAMPAC algorithms for AC/DC hybrid power systems, integrated in the InterSCADA platform, will be showcased, utilizing PMU measurements to estimate the magnitude and phase angle of electrical phasor quantities (such as voltage or current) in the grid, synchronized through a common time source. These algorithms, supported by a PDC that collects, processes, and synchronizes real-time phasor measurements from multiple PMUs, can trigger alarms for various operational events, including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When specific operating conditions, such as long, lightly loaded or open-ended transmission lines, cause the voltage to exceed the predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When a disturbance causes a power system oscillation and the frequency, amplitude, and damping of the power oscillation exceeds the predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When a significant disturbance in the transmission system causes increased RoCoF that exceeds the predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When an unintentional division of an interconnected power grid into individual disconnected regions takes place, i.e., islanding, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When a significant reduction in system equivalent inertia occurs due to limited synchronous generators, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When a fault has occurred in the protected zone, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI. • When the ancillary services are activated due to frequency deviation or power oscillations in the transmission system, active power set points for the GRITA HVDC link are sent to the dispatchers via the GUI.
Related business case(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid observability • Stability of the power grid • Power converter control

6.1.3. Key performance indicators (KPI)

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned demo objectives</i>
KPI_01	Number of modular microservices integrated in the service layer of InterSCADA platform	The developed software algorithms, for the monitoring and control of the AC/DC grids, are translated as microservices and constitute the modular components of the InterSCADA platform. The target in this demo is to integrate 7 modular microservices in the service layer of InterSCADA platform	Validate monitoring and control services in a hybrid AC/DC context
KPI_02	Number of external legacy systems interconnected with InterSCADA platform	By implementing an open-source SCADA system and enabling multi-vendor compatibility, interoperability among different components and systems can be achieved. The target in this demo is to interconnect the legacy PDC system of IPTO with InterSCADA platform	Demonstrate the ability of the InterSCADA platform to process real PMU data and detect key system events
KPI_03	Number of data structures integrated in the GUI	The different signals and alarms generated by the microservices will be organized and stored in a tailored data structure to efficiently manage and access them, enabling users and systems to effectively organize, store, and manipulate data in the GUI. The target is to integrate 7 data structures in the GUI (1 per service evaluated in the Greek Demo).	Improve grid observability
KPI_04	Number of modes detected in the Wide Area Monitoring, Protection, and Control (WAMPAC)	From the point of view of the TSO, it is crucial to avoid any frequency oscillations that could disrupt the safe operation of the system or have a negative effect on the power system elements—stress, increased losses, shorter lifespan, etc. Two basic conditions will be defined in the search for these kinds of oscillations. First, an amplitude threshold and second a minimum duration of the oscillations. In this demo it is expected to detect 5 modes of interest through the WAMPAC system.	Enhance the stability of power systems
KPI_05	Percentage increase of oscillations detected	The large-scale integration of RES generation with PE interfaces in the HETS presents new operational and stability challenges for the grid such as increased power oscillations. In demo case the target is to increase by 30% the oscillation detected.	Compare WAMPAC to conventional SCADA
KPI_06	Number of PMUs integrated in the InterSCADA platform	18 PMUs are installed in the HETS that can provide time-synchronized information with high resolution and in particular three-phase measurements of currents and voltages (magnitude, phase and frequency). Target of this demo is to integrate all of the 18 PMUs in the InterSCADA platform.	Demonstrate the ability of the InterSCADA platform to process real PMU data and detect key system events
KPI_07	Percentage reduction of ROCOF via stability countermeasures	Stability countermeasures provided from hybrid ac/dc power systems will be proposed that can reduce the ROCOF (such as frequency support). Target of this demo is to showcase that under	Enhance the stability of power systems

		some scenarios a 20% ROCOF reduction can be achieved via stability countermeasures.	
KPI_08	Percentage increase in the accuracy of detected RoCoFs	With increased RES generation with PE interfaces and HVDC links, grid inertia decreases, leading to faster frequency changes and higher RoCoF values, making accurate measurement more difficult. Target of this demo is to achieve 20% increase in the accuracy of detected RoCoFs compared to legacy systems.	Improve grid observability
KPI_09	Percentage increase of detected system splits	Utilizing the WAMPAC system an increase in the fast real-time detection of system splits and islanding events will be aimed. Target of this demo is to increase 40% the real-time detection of system splits.	Enhance the stability of power systems
KPI_10	Percentage increase of detected voltage instabilities	Utilizing the WAMPAC system, an increase in detected voltage instabilities will be aimed. Target of this demo is to increase 20% the detected voltage instabilities.	Enhance the stability of power systems

6.1.4. Demo conditions

Demo conditions
Assumptions
Real-time measurements from PMUs/PDC are needed.
Prerequisites
InterSCADA platform receives PMU measurements via the existing PDC with IEEE C37.118 protocol.
Demo conditions
Assumptions
Accurate alarms and set points are provided from the WAMPAC system when specific operational events take place.
Prerequisites
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All the aforementioned services (e.g., detection of overvoltages, power oscillations, sudden changes in frequency, etc.) have been developed and integrated to the InterSCADA platform. 2. The InterSCADA platform must be able to achieve interoperability with an appropriate protocol for receiving real-time measurements from PMUs.
Demo conditions
Assumptions
Remote access of partners to InterSCADA platform is needed during the demonstration to monitor the performance of the different algorithms and fine tune them when required.
Prerequisites
Remote access must be established while guaranteeing cybersecurity of IPTO's system. To support this use case, a Linux-based virtual machine will be hosted on IPTO premises, providing access to developers for platform deployment and testing.
Demo conditions
Assumptions
The Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been developed for the InterSCADA platform.

Prerequisites
 The GUI developed for the InterSCADA platform is user-friendly and intuitive for dispatchers.

6.2. Diagrams of demo

6.3. Technical details

6.3.1. Actors

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Measurements devices		Measurements devices provide values of the required real-time information of the power grid	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
PMU	Device	A PMU is a device used to estimate the magnitude and phase angle of an electrical phasor quantity (such as voltage or current) in the electricity grid using a common time source for synchronization. Time synchronization is usually provided by GPS, which allows synchronized real-time measurements of multiple remote points on the grid. PMUs can also be used to measure the frequency in the power grid. A typical commercial PMU can report measurements with high temporal resolution, up to 100 measurements per second for 50Hz power systems.	The PMUs installed in the Hellenic electricity transmission system report 50 measurements per second.
Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Control microservices		Control microservices: a) provide alarms or warnings that inform the Control Centre when a specific threshold is reached, b) calculate the set points for active power to be provided to PE for frequency support and oscillation damping services.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Overvoltage detection microservice	Software	An alarm is sent when an overvoltage is detected in the transmission system.	
Power oscillation detection microservice	Software	This service executes a continuous online modal analysis of the active power transfer to estimate the frequency, amplitude, and damping of their respective oscillations, and to trigger alarms on the Control Centre when low-damped local or inter-area oscillations of relevant amplitudes and frequencies are detected before the amplitudes become critically high and a local protection trip a heavily loaded line.	
RoCoF monitoring microservice	Software	An alarm is sent when the rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) exceeds a specific threshold that is considered critical.	
Islanding detection microservice	Software	An alarm is sent when islanded operation or loss of synchronism is detected.	
Inertia monitoring microservice	Software	An alarm is sent when the calculated inertia is below a predetermined limit.	

Fault detection microservice	Software	An alarm is sent when a fault is detected inside the protected zone.	
Ancillary control microservice	Software	Ancillary services calculate active power setpoints for the HVDC link known as GRITA.	

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Other actors		A summary of all actors that are no sensors or microservices	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Transmission System	System	An electrical transmission system is a network that transfers electrical power from generating stations (such as power plants) to distribution networks or end users. Main components of an electrical transmission system are the transmission lines, substations and transformers	
InterSCADA platform	Software	InterSCADA platform implements advanced services for real-time monitoring, control, and ancillary services	
Server	Hardware	A linux-based virtual machine will be hosted on IPTO premises, to host the InterSCADA platform	
PDC	Device	A Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC) collects, processes, and synchronizes real-time phasor measurements from multiple PMUs before sending them to control centres or other PDCs	
Dispatchers	Human	Dispatchers constantly monitor the transmission system and take remedial actions when needed	
GUI	Software	A GUI developed for the InterSCADA platform, which assists the dispatchers in monitoring and managing the AC/DC system.	

6.4. Step by step analysis of demo

6.4.1. Overview of use cases

Use case conditions		
No.	Use case name	Use case description
01	Overvoltage detection	A long, lightly loaded transmission line causes the voltage to rise
	Primary actor	PMUs

<i>Use case conditions</i>		
No.		
	Triggering event	An overvoltage occurs in a bus
	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the overvoltage detection microservice is running
	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
02	Use case name	Power oscillation
	Use case description	Large load changes or other external disturbances can cause power system oscillations
	Primary actor	PMUs
	Triggering event	Detection of low-damped local or inter-area oscillations with critical amplitudes
	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the power oscillation detection microservice is running
	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
03	Use case name	Critical RoCoF
	Use case description	Significant disturbances in the transmission system can cause increased RoCoF
	Primary actor	PMUs
	Triggering event	RoCoF increases to that extent that could compromise system stability and security.
	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the RoCoF monitoring microservice is running
04	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
	Use case name	Islanding event
	Use case description	An unintentional division of an interconnected power grid into individual disconnected regions with their own power generation takes place
	Primary actor	PMUs
	Triggering event	The system parameters including voltage, current, impedance, power, or frequency are monitored and show significant variations when an islanding event takes place
05	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the islanding detection microservice is running
	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
	Use case name	Low inertia
	Use case description	Large-scale production of renewable energy replaces synchronous generators with large mechanical rotating inertia and strong disturbance resilience, can result in a significant reduction in system equivalent inertia
	Primary actor	PMUs
06	Triggering event	Evaluation of reduced inertia based on a predetermined threshold
	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the inertia monitoring microservice is running
	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
	Use case name	Fault in transmission system
	Use case description	Generation from RES using PE behaves differently compared to synchronous generators during transient events. In terms of short-circuit current, RES with PE have a short-circuit current level that is limited by the power electronics' capacity. Furthermore, their short-circuit waveform depends on the type of control implemented on the PE. In this context, various issues have been identified for the behaviour of traditional short-circuit protection in electric power systems with high penetration of RES that utilize PE
	Primary actor	PMUs
07	Triggering event	A fault occurs in the protected Zone
	Pre-condition	InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and fault detection microservice is running
	Post-condition	Alarm is activated
	Use case name	Ancillary Services

Use case conditions	
No.	
	<p>Use case description</p> <p>Guidelines have been published for participation of HVDC systems in power system operation support in ENTSO-E area. For instance, the guidelines allow the TSO to require the HVDC system to control the active (and reactive) power output to maintain stable AC system, provide synthetic inertia in event of frequency deviation in the connected AC system and oscillation damping</p>
	<p>Primary actor</p> <p>PMUs</p>
	<p>Triggering event</p> <p>Events of frequency deviation or power oscillation</p>
	<p>Pre-condition</p> <p>InterSCADA platform is receiving real-time measurements from PMUs and the ancillary control microservice is running</p>
	<p>Post-condition</p> <p>Ancillary Services setpoints for the GRITA HVDC link</p>

6.4.2. Steps – Use cases

6.4.2.1. Use case #1

Use case #1 description

Overvoltage monitoring with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Overvoltage detection						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	A long, lightly loaded transmission line causes the voltage to rise	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs the overvoltage detection algorithm	Executes overvoltage detection	The overvoltage detection algorithm calculates the amplitude of the voltage	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Comparison with voltage threshold	Determine if an alarm must be activated	The overvoltage detection algorithm checks if the amplitude of the voltage exceeds the predetermined limit	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When the amplitude of the voltage exceeds the predetermined	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

Use case								
Use case name		Overvoltage detection						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
			limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI					

6.4.2.2. Use case #2

Use case #2 description

Power oscillation monitoring with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Power oscillation						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	A disturbance causes a power system oscillation	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs power oscillation detection algorithm	Executes power oscillation detection	The power oscillation detection algorithm calculates the frequency, amplitude, and damping of the oscillation	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Comparison with frequency, amplitude, and damping threshold	Determine if an alarm must be activated	The power oscillation detection algorithm checks if frequency, amplitude, and damping exceed the predetermined limit	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When the frequency, amplitude, and damping of the	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

Use case								
Use case name		Power oscillation						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
			power oscillation exceeds the predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI					

6.4.2.3. Use case #3

Use case #3 description

RoCoF monitoring with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Critical RoCoF						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	A significant disturbance in the transmission system causes increased RoCoF	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs the Critical RoCoF algorithm	Executes Critical RoCoF algorithm	The Critical RoCoF algorithm calculates the RoCoF	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Comparison with RoCoF threshold	Determine if an alarm must be activated	The Critical RoCoF algorithm checks if the RoCoF exceeds the predetermined limit	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When the RoCoF exceeds the predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

6.4.2.4. Use case #4

Use case #4 description

Monitoring islanding events with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Islanding event						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	An unintentional division of an interconnected power grid into individual disconnected regions takes place	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs islanding detection algorithm	Executes islanding detection algorithm	The islanding detection algorithm checks if there is an islanding event	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Islanding event detected	Determine if an islanding event has taken place	The islanding detection algorithm checks if an islanding event has taken place	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When an islanding event has taken place, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

6.4.2.5. Use case #5

Use case #5 description

Monitoring system equivalent inertia with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Low inertia						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Significant reduction in system inertia occurs due to limited synchronous generators	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs inertia algorithm	Executes system equivalent inertia estimation	The algorithm calculates system equivalent inertia to identify low inertia scenarios	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Comparison of inertia threshold	Determine if an alarm must be activated	The inertia algorithm checks if the equivalent inertia is lower than a predetermined limit	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When the inertia is lower than a predetermined limit, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

6.4.2.6. Use case #6

Use case #6 description

Monitoring faults with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Fault in transmission system						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	A fault occurs in the protected Zone	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06

Use case								
Use case name		Fault in transmission system						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
02	InterSCADA platform runs fault detection algorithm	Executes fault detection algorithm	The fault detection algorithm checks if there is fault in the protected zone	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-03, Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05
03	Fault detected	Determine if fault has taken place in the protected zone	The fault detection algorithm checks if a fault has occurred in the protected zone	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07
04	Inform dispatchers	Activation of alarm	When fault has occurred in the protected zone, an alarm is sent to the dispatchers via the GUI	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-04	Co-Is-08

6.4.2.7. Use case #7

Use case #7 description

Providing frequency support and power oscillation damping with InterSCADA platform

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Ancillary services						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Frequency deviation or power oscillations occurs in the transmission system	PMUs sending captured measurements from the event	PMUs send the measurements from the event to InterSCADA platform via PDC	REPORT	PMU	InterSCADA platform	I-01	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
02	InterSCADA platform runs Ancillary Services algorithm	Executes Ancillary Services algorithm	The Ancillary Services algorithm detects if there is a frequency deviation or a power oscillation	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-02	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
03	Set points of active power	Determine active power set points	The Ancillary Services	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I-03	Co-Is-07

Use case								
Use case name		Ancillary services						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
			algorithm calculates active power set points					
04	Inform dispatchers	Provide active power set points	When the ancillary services are activated active power set points are sent to the dispatchers via the GUI	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	GUI/Dispatchers	I-05	Co-Is-08

6.5. Information exchanged

Information exchanged			
Information exchanged, ID	Name of information exchanged	Description of information exchanged	Requirement, R-IDs
I-01	Measurement from PMUs	The PMU estimates the magnitude and phase angle of an electrical phasor quantity (such as voltage or current) and sends it to the PDC. The PDC captures data from the different PMUs installed in the transmission system, which are then fed into the InterSCADA platform.	Co-Is-01, Co-Is-02, Co-Is-03
I-02	Input for algorithms	InterSCADA platform sends PMU measurements for the execution of the different algorithms.	Co-Is-04, Co-Is-05, Co-Is-06
I-03	Results from the algorithm	The output result of the algorithms is sent for evaluation to determine if the transmission system is in any critical situation.	Co-Is-07
I-04	Alarms	An alarm is sent to the GUI when the InterSCADA platform concludes that the transmission system is in a critical situation.	Co-Is-08
I-05	Set points	Set points for active power are send to the GUI when the ancillary services are activated.	Co-Is-08

6.6. Requirements

Requirements (optional)		
Categories ID	Category name for requirements	Category description
Co-Is	Configuration issues	Configuration issues reflect the communication configurations that are relevant to a use case step. These configuration issues include numbers of devices and/or systems, distances, communication types, existing protocols (e.g. C37.118).
Requirement ID	Requirement name	Requirement description
Co-Is-01	Latency	A low-latency communication must be established
Co-Is-02	Protocol	InterSCADA platform must be able to receive PMU measurements via the existing PDC with IEEE C37.118 protocol
Co-Is-03	Virtual machine	A Linux-based virtual machine must be available to host the InterSCADA platform

Co-Is-04	Data translation	PMU data must be converted to json format
Co-Is-05	Routing process	PMU data must be directed to the microservices
Co-Is-06	Database storage	A sufficient data storage must exist to store the large amount of data produced by the PMUs
Co-Is-07	Algorithm reaction time	The algorithm reaction time must satisfy the algorithm requirements.
Co-Is-08	Protocol	IEC 104 protocol must be supported for future connection with EMS/SCADA of IPTO.

7. Demo 3 Specifications

7.1. Description of the demo

The Spanish power system is undergoing a profound structural transformation, driven by the rapid integration of non-dispatchable renewable generation—primarily wind and solar—and the increasing electrification of demand. The National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) defined by the Spanish Government sets ambitious targets for the deployment of renewable energy: 81% renewable generation by 2030. This evolution introduces significant operational complexity in the real-time management of the transmission network.

Wind and solar generation technologies are based on variable and uncertain resources and use power electronics converters as interfaces with the grid connection to commit the power injection requirements. That represents a replacement of traditional synchronous generation by power electronic converter-based generation, introducing challenges in comparison with the traditional, well-known performance and operation of power systems. Some of these challenges are the limitations to provide inertia, fault current as well as possible control algorithm iterations.

Deployment of specific DC based technologies integrated in the transmission system provides additional extended control capabilities for system operation in comparison to the traditional AC power networks if they operate as expected. This fact represents an opportunity to increase system flexibility and deal with the previous challenges introduced by non-dispatchable renewable generation. Technologies like High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) links and flexible transmission systems based on power electronics (e.g., STATCOMs or power flow controllers) are representatives of this DC-based technologies. They enhance system flexibility, providing capabilities both for power balance and system stability.

In the case of Spain, the following DC-based technologies have been deployed, demonstrating provision of enhanced flexibility for power system operation:

- Spain–France HVDC (Baixas–Santa Llogaia): based on voltage source converter (VSC) technology and with an exchange capacity of 2 x 1000 MW.
- Iberian Peninsula- Balearic Islands HVDC: based on line-commutated converter (LCC) technology and in. raw exchange capacity of 2 x 400 MW.
- Static Series Synchronous Compensator (SSSC) Torres de Segre: 50 MVar power electronics device capable of modifying the power flow in the line and reduce network congestion.

Other projects are currently under execution to take advantage of their capabilities for the energy transmission and power system operation:

- HVDC Golfo de Vizcaya: new submarine interconnection between Spain and France based on VSC technology and with an exchange capacity of 2 x 1000 MW.

- HVDC Iberian Peninsula-Balearic Islands II: new HVDC link based on VSC technology and grid forming capability, 2x200MW.
- STATCOM: deployment of 4 STATCOM in different locations in the Spanish Grid.

In addition to the traditional controllable equipment in AC systems (such as open/close lines, phase-shift transformers, generators setpoints, etc.), all these additional controllable DC devices have to be properly operated in a coordinated way to extract the maximum value to the system. The SCADA and Energy Management System (EMS) in control centres, and optimization algorithms running within the EMS, play a key role in properly defining the optimal setpoints of those controllable devices. Optimal optimization power flow algorithms have been traditionally used in power systems dispatch and operation. However, the size of real transmission systems - composed of hundreds and thousands of buses- and the increased controllable variables in real hybrid AC/DC systems represent a very complex mathematical optimization problem with demonstrated limitations to be used in real-time operation of power systems (e.g., 5 min intervals between snapshots). The main limitations of these algorithms are feasibility (to converge to a feasible solution), accuracy (to find the absolute optimum) and computational time (to obtain the result in an time that will be useful for real-time operation). In addition, the magnitude of the problem is increased when applied for contingency analysis, which means to evaluate the optimal setpoints for the different possible contingencies that might occur in the network.

Simplifications have been traditionally applied to the mentioned optimal power flow formulation in order to achieve convergence of the algorithm, such as DC OPF. However, the simplifications imply lack of additional information and accuracy and do not model the different operational modes of the HVDC and other controllable devices. Development of Artificial Intelligence algorithms, together with the unprecedented increase of computational hardware capabilities, represent an opportunity to handle the above-mentioned computational limitations for real-time operation of power systems with high penetration of non-dispatchable renewable generation.

This demo focuses on the implementation and evaluation of different algorithms for EMS applied for real-time optimal operation of real hybrid AC/DC power systems equipped with enhanced control capabilities and high-presence of non-dispatchable renewable generation. Performance of more advanced optimization algorithms developed in InterSCADA project will be tested first to determine optimal operation of the system under normal operation conditions (system out of contingency) and then for the identification of potential remedial actions to maintain the system within the operational limits.

7.1.1. Name of demo

<i>Demo identification</i>	
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name of demo</i>
	Demonstration of new advanced optimization algorithms for optimal setpoints and remedial actions calculation in hybrid AC/DC system based on Artificial Intelligence: application case to the Spanish Control Centre

7.1.2. Scope and objectives of demo

Scope and objectives of demo	
Scope	<p>The Spanish TSOs is playing a crucial role to integrate variable renewable power into the system and preserve the reliability and security of the power supply. The high penetration of variable renewable generation based on power electronics converters introduces increased complexity and uncertainty in the TSO Control Centre activity and the development of more advanced additional tools is expected to continue dealing with these challenges. In addition to that, existing and new HVDC links, as well as other DC-based controllable devices (e.g., FACTS, energy storage) are demonstrated to contribute to these renewable penetration mission and flexibility provision. Therefore, new tools for the Control Centre SCADA-EMS system and controllable devices can contribute to the reliable operation of hybrid AC/DC power systems.</p> <p>Control Centre operators are continuously analysing the right performance of the transmission system and applying appropriate actions to preserve the system within the right operational margins of voltage and power. Examples of these actions are connection/disconnection of power lines, managing generation level, adjusting setpoints of controllable devices or connecting/disconnecting voltage control equipment. However, with the increased complexity and uncertainty previously mentioned, decisions of operators are exposed to more complex scenarios and available controllable devices should be optimally operated and coordinated for the system operation.</p>
Objective(s)	<p>To test capabilities of advanced optimal power flow tools for operation of hybrid AC/DC power systems applied in the Control Centre</p> <p>To evaluate algorithms performance: feasible optimal solution valid for real-time operation of the power system</p> <p>To evaluate potential to determine remedial actions to maintain the system operation within the appropriate limits.</p>
Short description	<p>The aim of the demonstrator is to test the application and capabilities of advanced optimization tools, such as AC optimal power flow and security constraint power flow, applied to hybrid AC-DC network operation under near-real-time conditions (5-10 minutes).</p>
Complete description	<p>The Spanish control centre demo of the InterSCADA project aims to implement a test environment to validate, under near real-time conditions (with execution intervals between 5-10 minutes), the optimal operation tools and artificial intelligence artefacts developed in other work packages, such as AC-OPF OPF-SC (Optimal Power Flow under Security Constraints). This demo focuses on the operation of the Spanish transmission system including hybrid AC/DC networks.</p> <p>The environment integrates the following components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EMS (Energy Management System) module of the InterSCADA platform with the new algorithms developed. • The HMI (Human Machine Interface) module. • A control centre emulator. • A database containing grid scenarios and real measurements from the Spanish Control Centre. <p>The EMS and HMI modules developed within the project will be integrated with the software components specifically developed for the demo, including the control centre emulator and the real-time measurement database. The model of the Spanish transmission grid will also be incorporated into the demo.</p> <p>All necessary tests to validate the correct integration of these software modules will be carried out. In parallel, the grid scenarios to be used for result analysis will be selected.</p> <p>Once this integration phase is complete, the demo will be ready to assess the performance of the new developments of the InterSCADA platform, with a particular focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EMS module with the new optimal power flow developments

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The AI-based artifact that generates operational recommendations for system operators in complex scenarios. <p>Specifically, AI models for OPF-SC will be implemented and executed through autonomous agents designed to ensure that execution times remain below the thresholds required for near real-time operation (i.e., under 10 minutes). These algorithms will be responsible for processing input data, running the optimization models, and delivering actionable recommendations within the defined time constraints. Specifically, they will provide support through the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose optimal and remedial actions in real-time under complex operational conditions that present decision-making challenges for system operators. Recommend possible actions in the grid, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Topology modifications (e.g., breaker operations). Adjustments to power and voltage setpoints in generators, HVDC links, and FACTS devices. Learn from historical and real-time grid conditions as well as from operator decisions and actions. Operate in both real-time and near real-time environments, ensuring responsiveness and adaptability to evolving grid states. <p>During this phase, system operators from Red Eléctrica will actively participate in testing the tools and evaluating the results, with the aim of assessing their potential application in actual system operation practices.</p>
<p>Related case(s)</p>	<p>The main economic benefits associated with this demo are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the reliability of the power system operation incorporating hybrid AC-DC elements and reduce the risk of power supply interruptions to society Increase the penetration levels of renewable power generation while supporting the operation under the uncertainty and variability caused by these renewable sources Reduce potential redispatch of power generation

7.1.3. Key performance indicators (KPI)

Key performance indicators			
ID	Name	Description	Reference to mentioned demo objectives
KPI_1	Computational time	Computational time of the new developed algorithm, calculated for the different cases evaluated. Computational times <=5 min	To evaluate algorithms performance
KPI_2	Algorithm convergence	Number of times and % the algorithm converges and not converge from the total of simulations conducted	To evaluate algorithms performance
KPI_3	Power exchange optimisation	Optimisation of the HVDCs setpoints and control modes: comparison of setpoints calculated by the new algorithms developed versus the traditional method used (power flow modes calculation by operator)	To evaluate algorithms performance
KPI_4	Remedial actions performance	Comparison of the remedial actions proposed by the new algorithms versus the current remedial actions calculated by the operators for the same scenarios.	To evaluate potential to determine remedial actions

7.1.4. Demo conditions

Demo conditions

Assumptions
Data exchanges with REE's SCADA/EMS system are functional and complete. State estimation data sufficient for new algorithms performance evaluation.
Prerequisites
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data exchange with border countries available for HVDC interconnections operation 2. Format of the data files exchange is appropriated.
Demo conditions
Assumptions
Sufficient data for effective AI agent training
Prerequisites
Receive historical databases (with the multiple electrical measurements in the control centre) from the system operators for all the weeks selected, with 5 minutes granularity.

Demo conditions
Assumptions
Computational time and convergence of the new tools and algorithm developed are appropriated for system operation (this assumption will be checked during the evaluation phase of the demonstrator)
Prerequisites
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pre – training of the algorithm with synthetic or real data. 2. Data are appropriated for the real power system operation and therefore can be used in the new algorithms.

7.2. Diagrams of demo

Figure 9 provides a high level diagram of the demo:

Figure 9: Diagram of demo 3

Figure 10 shows the communication architecture and remedial actions agent implementation based on heuristic algorithms:

Figure 10: Communication architecture and remedial actions agent implementation

7.3. Technical details

The following devices and remedial are considered by the new algorithms developed to provide remedial actions for reliable and optimal power system operation:

Device	Remedial action
Phase Shifting Transformers	Tap position change
HVDC	Setpoints modification, power exchange modification
STATCOM, other FACTS	Setpoints modification, power exchange modification

Transmission power line, power transformers, circuit breakers	Connection/disconnection
Reactors/inductors	Connection/disconnection
Tap-changer transformer	Tap position change
Power generators	Remote disconnection, automatic power reduction, voltage control

7.3.1. Actors

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Platforms			
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
SCADA/EMS system	System	Key information about the transmission grid and status will be extracted from this system. It includes information such as grid model, grid status parameters, etc.	
New EMS module	System	This module allocates the new algorithms developed in the project for optimal operation and remedial actions. These algorithms are responsible for calculating and sending to the interface with the operator the setpoints calculated and the remedial actions. Computational times and accuracy are key criteria for the evaluation of these algorithms.	
Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Operators			
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Control room operator	Human	Responsible for reliable system operation and execute the required remedial actions. This actor will receive recommendation of remedial actions determined by the algorithms and evaluate the appropriateness of the setpoints generated by the optimization algorithms and the proposed remedial actions	

7.4. Step by step analysis of demo

7.4.1. Overview of use cases

<i>Use case conditions</i>		
No.		
01	Use case name	Training the AI agent
	Use case description	<p>The training and validation of the algorithms developed in this demo will rely on historical data provided by Red Eléctrica. These datasets will be delivered in open format with an hourly resolution, ensuring interoperability and seamless integration into simulation environments. Representative scenarios have been defined based on time series with hourly granularity, strategically selected throughout the year to capture a broad spectrum of operating conditions in the power system. These include seasonal demand variations, renewable generation patterns, and different topological configurations of the grid.</p> <p>The evaluation of the algorithms will be carried out on different electrical network models, following a progressive approach that scales from simple systems to the complete real system:</p> <p>Reference systems (e.g., IEEE 30-bus): These will be used as an initial testbed due to their simplicity, public availability, and widespread use. They will serve to validate core algorithmic logic, test control setpoints, and fine-tune parameters.</p> <p>Spain–France transmission system – simplified version: A reduced model of the real system with fewer nodes but maintaining the overall network structure. Suitable for intermediate tests that require greater realism while preserving manageable simulation times.</p> <p>Spain–France transmission system – full version: A detailed representation of the real system used in the control centre, including all network elements. This model allows for a realistic assessment of the algorithms' effectiveness and robustness.</p> <p>Spain–France transmission system with planned expansions: A version of the full model that incorporates expected future developments in the transmission network, enabling evaluation under evolving grid conditions.</p> <p>As part of this demo, a control agent based on Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques will be developed. The agent will be composed of a neural network, whose weights will be optimized using metaheuristic algorithms. Training will occur through interaction with an environment that simulates a power system including HVDC links.</p> <p>The training strategy will follow a phased approach: Initial stage: Training on a reduced system (IEEE 30-bus) including an HVDC link. Intermediate stage: Training on a representative model of the Spanish transmission system interconnected with France via HVDC. Final stage: Validation on the full-scale model of the Spanish transmission grid, with the HVDC link fully modelled.</p> <p>The goal of the agent is to identify contingencies within the system and generate control setpoints that restore operational variables to within acceptable limits. By leveraging real historical data with hourly resolution, the training environment will realistically reflect operational conditions, allowing thorough validation of the agent's behaviour under complex and realistic scenarios.</p>
	Primary actor	New EMS module
	Triggering event	Training starts
	Pre-condition	AI agent in development
	Post-condition	AI agent ready for testing

<i>Use case conditions</i>		
No.		
02	Use case name	Evaluating developed algorithms and IA agent performance
	Use case description	Selection of representative time periods throughout the year to reflect diverse grid operating conditions and renewable generation variability. Processing of historical datasets with hourly resolution, provided by Red Eléctrica in open format, including various electrical measurements recorded in the control centre. Simulation of modified scenarios: Controlled perturbations will be introduced into the historical datasets to assess the algorithms' performance under unforeseen conditions, validating their robustness and adaptability. Suggested remedial actions are compared against the actions calculated by operators.
	Primary actor	New EMS module
	Triggering event	Receiving measurements
	Pre-condition	AI agent ready for testing
	Post-condition	AI agent verified in normal operation

7.4.2. Steps – Use cases

7.4.2.1. Use case #1

Use case #1 description

Training AI agent

Use case step by step analysis

<i>Use case</i>								
<i>Use case name</i>		Training AI agent						
No.	Event	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>	<i>Service</i>	<i>Information producer (actor)</i>	<i>Information receiver (actor)</i>	<i>Inf. exchanged (IDs)</i>	<i>Requirements (IDs)</i>
01		Developing training models	Developing power system models of increasing complexity that will be used to train the AI agent		Operators	New EMS module	IE_07	
02		Running training models	Using the different test networks to train the AI agent		Operators	New EMS module		

7.4.2.2. Use case #2

Use case #2 description

Evaluating developed algorithms and IA agent performance

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Evaluating developed algorithms and IA agent performance						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01		Selecting scenarios	Determine representative scenarios to serve as baseline. Modify baseline scenario by adding controlled perturbations will be introduced		Operators			
02		Process datasets	Process the datasets for both baseline scenarios and modified scenarios		New EMS module			
03		Evaluate suggested remedial actions	Compare the remedial actions proposed by the new software to those suggested/calculated by operators for the same scenarios.		Operators			

7.5. Information exchanged

Information exchanged			
Information exchanged, ID	Name of information exchanged	Description of information exchanged	Requirement, R-IDs
IE_01	Data from the state estimator in Red Eléctrica's EMS	The algorithms receive as input power system scenarios containing all necessary information (demand, generation, topology, etc.). This data is stored in the control centre database and emulates the output of the state estimator. Delivered in open format with hourly resolution.	R_01, R_02
IE_02	Historical SCADA/EMS data	Archived operational measurements provided by Red Eléctrica in open format with hourly granularity. Used to train and validate AI algorithms, and to define representative scenarios. Includes load, generation, breaker status, etc.	R_03
IE_03	Forecasted system scenarios	Predicted conditions of demand and renewable generation profiles, used for preventive optimization and risk anticipation.	R_04

Information exchanged			
Information exchanged, ID	Name of information exchanged	Description of information exchanged	Requirement, R-IDs
IE_04	Operator actions log	Historical records of actions taken by system operators in response to contingencies or optimization events. Used as input for learning-based models.	R_05
IE_05	AI-generated setpoints and remedial actions	Outputs of the optimization and AI algorithms: proposed control actions, equipment setpoints, and topological reconfigurations. Specifically, the reinforcement learning-based agent will generate setpoints intended to restore operational variables to acceptable limits.	R_06
IE_06	Operator feedback on proposed actions	Feedback from human operators regarding the actions proposed by the AI system, including acceptance, rejection, or adjustment of recommendations.	R_07
IE_07	Grid model (topology and parameters)	Electrical model of the transmission system: bus connectivity, line impedances, equipment ratings and operational constraints. Used for simulation, optimization, and training environments.	R_08
IE_08	Configuration files (.raw, etc.)	Structured simulation inputs and grid configurations used internally by optimization agents. Transferred via MQTT in segmented format. Compatible with reference test systems (e.g., IEEE 30-bus) and real transmission grid models.	R_09

7.6. Requirements

Requirements will be defined in more detail in a dedicated document.

Requirements		
Requirements ID	Description of requirement	Category
R_01	The system must provide access to real-time operational data from REE's SCADA/EMS platform, including the output of the state estimator. These data should be made available in open, standardized formats (e.g., CSV, JSON) and delivered with a minimum temporal resolution of one hour. This ensures seamless integration with simulation environments and alignment with the data structure expected by the AI training and evaluation pipelines.	Functional
R_02	The latency for real-time data exchange between the SCADA/EMS system and the AI platform must not exceed 1 minute, ensuring timely availability of information for contingency detection, decision-making, and reactive control. This is critical for the alignment of AI recommendations with real-time operation cycles and operator situational awareness.	Performance
R_03	REE must provide historical datasets spanning at least 12 consecutive months, containing operational measurements such as power flows, generation profiles, and breaker status. These datasets must be provided in open format and with an hourly resolution, suitable for training and validating machine learning models. They will be used to build representative scenarios that reflect seasonal variability and topological differences throughout the year.	Data Availability
R_04	A forecasting module must generate system condition scenarios (demand and renewable generation) with prediction horizons of	Functional / Accuracy

<i>Requirements</i>		
<i>Requirements ID</i>	<i>Description of requirement</i>	<i>Category</i>
	24–48 hours. The outputs must have hourly resolution, and the forecasts should be updated every 10 minutes to reflect the most recent trends. These forecasts are essential for enabling proactive grid operation and risk anticipation within the AI algorithms.	
R_05	To support supervised learning and continuous improvement of AI agents, historical logs of operator actions in response to past events (e.g., contingencies, overloads, re-dispatch) must be made available. These logs must be structured and time-synchronized with SCADA events to allow correct contextual interpretation.	Data Governance
R_06	AI and optimization agents — including the reinforcement learning (RL) control agent trained using metaheuristic optimization algorithms — must be capable of returning a complete set of recommended control actions (e.g., reactive setpoints, switching commands, redispatch orders) within 10 minutes from scenario acquisition. This ensures alignment with the temporal constraints of grid operation and real-time decision loops.	Performance / Real-time
R_07	The human-machine interface (HMI) must incorporate a structured mechanism that enables operators to review, accept, reject, or modify the proposed actions generated by the AI system. This feedback loop must be intuitive and allow for traceable interaction, ensuring trust, transparency, and accountability in operator-AI collaboration.	Usability / Human Factors
R_08	The electrical grid models used for simulations and validation must follow a multi-stage structure, including: (1) reference systems such as the IEEE 30-bus network, (2) a simplified version of the Spain–France transmission grid, (3) the full operational model used by REE’s control centre, and (4) an extended version incorporating future grid developments. All models must be validated prior to testing to ensure simulation fidelity.	Technical / Integrity
R_09	Communication between modules must use the MQTT protocol, and must support the segmented transmission and reassembly of structured configuration files (e.g., .raw, .json). These files must be compatible with both reference models and the real transmission system models used in simulation and optimization engines.	Communication / Protocol
R_10	All data exchanged within the system must be protected using robust encryption protocols, such as TLS or equivalent. Additionally, the system must ensure full compliance with NIS2 and GDPR directives concerning cybersecurity and the protection of personal and operational data in critical infrastructures. This includes logging, access control, and secure storage mechanisms.	Security / Legal

8. Demo 4 Specifications

8.1. Description of the demo

The widespread deployment of Inverter-based resources (IBRs), alongside the increasing installation of High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) links - both embedded within Alternative Current (AC) grids and connecting different synchronous areas - is fundamentally transforming power system dynamics. It introduces new stability challenges, particularly in weak grids, while significantly altering traditional stability issues. The integration of IBRs affects classical stability problems by introducing novel dynamic responses that can interact with existing behaviours. Furthermore, the grid's traditional structure is changing: it no longer consists solely of large production centres supplying small, distributed loads. Instead, the generation mix now includes both large, centralized plants and numerous small, distributed units, while consumption patterns are evolving due to decarbonization efforts, resulting in large, localized loads. Given these developments, accurately modelling all components in stability studies becomes crucial. Another key consequence is increased volatility in operating conditions, making it difficult to predict the worst-case scenarios. Relying on predetermined stability limits can either become prohibitively expensive—if attempting to cover all possibilities—or insecure, if some critical scenarios are overlooked.

The French TSO, RTE, manages both the transmission and sub-transmission networks, covering voltage levels from 63 kV to 400 kV. The system comprises over 100 000 kilometres of lines, several thousand substations and an annual load of 446 TWh in 2023³. DC interconnections with neighbouring countries from continental Europe exist (2 * 1000 MW with Spain, 2 * 600 MW with Italy) as well as interconnections with Great Britain (IFA 2000, IFA2 and Eleclink links). Ambitious plans are underway to expand DC link infrastructure, both within the French grid and with neighbouring systems, as illustrated in Figure 11. Additionally, the share of IBR assets in France is expected to grow significantly, potentially matching the scale of the nuclear power sector. A major driver of this growth is the development of offshore wind farms, with large units being connected off the Atlantic coast and in the Mediterranean Sea. The newest installations will be connected through DC lines.

³ RTE annual review 2023 - <https://analysesetdonnees.rte-france.com/en/annual-review-2023/keyfindings>

Figure 11: Overview of HVDC interconnections and DC-connected offshore wind parks in France (source: <https://www.rte-international.com/en/power-electronics-and-studies/>)

All these changes have a significant impact on grid stability across the various aspects previously discussed. This demonstration focuses specifically on AC transient stability in the French system. Given the prominence of nuclear units in France, synchronous machine transient stability is critically important: maintaining sufficient security margins without excessively increasing costs is more than ever a challenge. To maximize the chance of having enough stability margins, large units—including IBRs and HVDC links—are required to provide stabilizing support, such as injecting reactive current during short-circuits. Nevertheless, despite these measures, risky situations are emerging under an increasing range of operating conditions and remain difficult to predict. A further complication arises because transient stability risks often coincide with high-voltage conditions, which present conflicting operational requirements: mitigating high voltage typically involves increasing reactive power consumption by generators, whereas improving transient stability calls for reducing reactive power consumption. This contradiction complicates operator decision-making.

Having a clear and accurate view of transient stability limits in close to real time or real time situations is therefore crucial for power grid operation. Currently, RTE relies on predetermined security limits to manage transient stability issues. However, this approach has two main limitations: in some cases, the margins are overly conservative, while in others, risky situations go undetected. An alternative approach based on real-time contingency analysis is being explored, but it also faces several challenges when used alone:

- Computation time remains a major obstacle for large-scale, high-accuracy time-domain analysis.
- Beyond simply assessing whether the system is stable or unstable, operators need actionable recommendations—such as control levers and their expected effectiveness in unstable scenarios—or margin evaluations when the system is stable.
- Running extensive online time-domain simulations demands a highly robust simulation engine, which is difficult to achieve. Developing an engine that is both accurate and robust while maintaining real-time performance appears to be a challenge.

This demonstration will showcase the relevance and benefits of an enhanced, flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis within the rapidly evolving AC/DC system. It will leverage intelligent, state-of-the-art modules designed to reduce reliance on costly time-domain simulations while representing the behaviour of IBRs and HVDC links.

8.1.1. Name of demo

<i>Demo identification</i>	
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name of demo</i>
	Enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis on the French system

8.1.2. Scope and objectives of demo

<i>Scope and objectives of demo</i>	
Scope	Demonstration of an enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis on the French system
Objective(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve situational awareness, especially for an AC/DC system • Avoid unnecessary and potentially costly preventive actions • Integrate innovative methods in the control room
Short description	An enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis - leveraging intelligent modules to reduce the reliance on complex and time-consuming time-domain computations - will be used to replicate analysis conducted in RTE's control room. This improved decision-support algorithm is expected to provide operators with a clearer view of transient stability risks in real time or close to real time. Differences between the dangerous events identified by the current method and those detected by the InterSCADA-developed approach will be thoroughly assessed and analysed to uncover their origins and underlying causes.
Complete description	<p>The demo involves the demonstration of an enhanced and flexible approach for real-time transient stability analysis applied to a large set of data from the French system. Rather than relying solely on time-domain analysis that are both computationally extensive and prone to robustness issues, this approach employs innovative modules to identify scenarios and reduce the complexity and scale of the simulated system. These advanced building blocks are combined and associated with classical simulation engines (state estimation, load flow engine and time-domain simulations), alongside advanced GUI and margin estimation.</p> <p>In this demo, the new decision-making process will be evaluated on the entire French system (see Figure 12) using a selected dataset exported from RTE's SCADA or EMS system in CIM/CGMES format. The exchanged data include measurements from conventional sensors (P, Q, V), topology information (breakers and disconnectors status – open/close, tap position for</p>

Figure 12: French power public transmission grid in 2025 (Available here - <https://assets.rte-france.com/prod/public/2025-04/2025-04-28-sddr-executive-summary.pdf> -, provided by RTE)

phase shifters, etc.) and system characteristics. The exchange will occur offline using historical data and transient stability analysis will be conducted every one hour.

P, Q and V measurements are derived from conventional CT and VT sensors and are available every 10 s in RTE's centralized SCADA/EMS system. Considering the entire RTE system along with the necessary part from the neighbouring systems, this involves approximately 15 000 active power measurements and 20 000 voltage and reactive power measurements. The French system itself comprises around 10 000 lines, 2 000 transformers and 6 000 substations – it is important to notice that there are also phase-shifter transformers in the system and that transformer tap positions are not directly available in the SCADA/EMS and must therefore be estimated. Currently, under normal operating conditions, more than 95 % of the system is observable, meaning RTE collects sufficient measurements to construct a complete and consistent system state across 95% of the network through state estimation.

The decision-making process will run automatically and deliver results via a user-friendly platform interface. Critical events and their consequences will be immediately visible, while additional information for the other cases must be easily accessible and interpretable. The results will be closely monitored and analysed to identify differences compared to the current decision-making process. In case of differences in the power system control and operation, they must be explained and justified to prove the added value of the newly proposed method. It is expected that additional critical events can be identified, or that unnecessary preventive actions can be avoided.

Related case(s)	business	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid transient stability assessment for system operators • Integration of advanced, innovative algorithms in the control room
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8.1.3. Key performance indicators (KPI)

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned demo objectives</i>
KPI_01	Efficient and robust screening method	<p>The performance of the screening method will be assessed on a selected set of data and the following thresholds must be reached:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robustness – number of executions without errors > 95 % • Computation time - /3 compared to full time domain analysis • Filtering effect > 75 % <p>A complete RMS time-domain simulation on the same system will be used as the reference.</p>	Integrate innovative methods in the control room
KPI_02	Efficient and robust network reduction techniques	<p>The performance of the network reduction technique will be assessed on a selected set of data and the following thresholds must be reached:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robustness – number of executions without errors > 95 % • Computation time - /2 compared to calculation on the complete network • Quality – < 10 % difference on critical clearing time <p>A complete RMS time-domain simulation on the initial (entire) system will be used as the reference.</p>	Integrate innovative methods in the control room
KPI_03	Enhanced and flexible approach for real time transient stability analysis	<p>The performance of the overall enhanced and flexible approach for real time transient stability analysis will be assessed on a selected set of data and the following thresholds are expected to be reached:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robustness – success rate > 95 % • Computation time - /2 in comparison with a workflow with only time domain simulations • Quality – number of dangerous cases correctly identified (~100 %) • Efficiency – additional margins and additional dangerous cases identified (*2 in terms of events simulated) <p>A decision-making method solely using RMS time-domain simulations on the entire system will be used as the reference.</p> <p>Comparisons with the current workflow purely based on predetermined rules will only be done qualitatively.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve situational awareness, especially for an AC/DC system • Avoid unnecessary and potentially costly preventive actions

8.1.4. Demo conditions

<i>Demo conditions</i>
Assumptions
Basic functions are already available, performant enough and robust in the platform selected for the InterSCADA project (SOGNO).
Prerequisites
For the demo to run properly and effectively, it is essential that basic functions (state estimation, power flow engine and time-domain simulation tool) are integrated in InterSCADA and run efficiently on large-scale systems with AC and DC components. Specifically, the state estimation function must conduct observability analysis and post-processing functions in addition to the state estimation itself. It must also run on large-scale (15 000 active power measurements and 20 000 reactive power measurements) situations, with real life data (disconnected busbar, erroneous data) and with advanced components such as phase-shifters, specific DC controllers (AC-emulation) or tap-changers (tap must be calculated). The load flow engine has similar requirements, needing to run on large-scale, real-world datasets. It must support classical functionalities such as PQ limits, tap changer adjustments, and phase shifter settings. For the time-domain simulation tool, RTE already has a functional engine (Dynawo), and the main task is its integration into the SOGNO platform. A critical aspect of this integration is ensuring the dynamic database is properly managed.
<i>Demo conditions</i>
Assumptions
Advanced functions have been developed during the project and are available in the InterSCADA platform (i.e. SOGNO).
Prerequisites
The filtering and reduction network engines have been developed during the project, are working as expected on large scale systems and are available in the InterSCADA platform. It should be easy to run them and to obtain the results in the platform.
<i>Demo conditions</i>
Assumptions
Decision-making process developed and available in the InterSCADA platform.
Prerequisites
The decision-making process that will call all the individual modules is available and validated in the InterSCADA platform. It must be possible to execute it automatically on a large set of data, with acceptable computation times, and to visualize the results in the GUI integrated into the InterSCADA platform and to access them offline for analysis.

8.2. Diagrams of demo

Figure 13: Complete decision-making process

8.3. Technical details

8.3.1. Actors

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
System operators		The different entities and persons responsible for monitoring, managing, and operating safely the grid.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Control room operator	Human	Information receiver. The control room operator will receive the result and diagnosis from the automatic workflow.	Active actor.
System stability expert	Human	Information provider. The system stability expert is responsible of preparing the list of countermeasures that may be tested in the process as well as the list of scenarios considered.	Active actor.
Tool developer	Human	The tool developer will be in charge to define the settings related to different parts of the automatic workflow, in particular criteria for screening or network reduction techniques.	Active actor.
Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Platforms		The platforms required to conduct the demonstration responsible for providing data and running the decision-making process.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
RTE SCADA/EMS	System	Information provider. Data from the data historian will be sent from the SCADA/EMS system to the InterSCADA platform to start the workflow.	Active actor
InterSCADA platform	System	Platform that will contain all the unitary treatments, and that will handle the whole process execution.	Active actor.

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
Individual modules		The different individual modules that may be used in the decision-making process.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
State Estimation Engine	Module	Performs the state estimation that starts the decision-making process.	Active actor.
Filtering engine	Module	Filters the dangerous events that needs to be simulated with a time-domain engine	Active actor
Network Reduction and Aggregation engine	Module	Performs a network reduction and aggregation of RES for time-domain simulation to increase robustness and performances	Active actor

Time domain engine	Module	Performs time-domain simulation on the reduced network.	Active actor.
Load flow engine	Module	Performs load flow calculations on the modified situation to provide a new system state	Active actor.

Actors			
Grouping (e.g., domains, zones)		Group description	
External resources		System actors whom information is required to evaluate margins and possible countermeasures for transient stability analysis.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this demo
Power plant producers	Resources	Information provider. Active power modulation capabilities, reactive power limitations.	Passive actor.

8.4. Step by step analysis of demo

8.4.1. Overview of use cases

Use case conditions		
No.	Use case name	Use case description
01	Use case name	Assess transient stability in real-time
	Use case description	The InterSCADA platform receives data from RTE's SCADA/EMS system, launches the transient stability assessment and provides results.
	Primary actor	InterSCADA platform (and all the other actors)
	Triggering event	Measurements receiving
	Pre-condition	
	Post-condition	

8.4.2. Steps – Use cases

8.4.2.1. Use case #1

Use case #1 description

Assess transient stability in real time

Use case step by step analysis

Use case								
Use case name		Assess transient stability in real time						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
01	Measurements available	Measurements received from the legacy	The measurements are received by the InterSCADA	REPORT	RTE SCADA/EMS	InterSCADA platform	I_01	

Use case								
Use case name		Assess transient stability in real time						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
	triggering the workflow	SCADA/EMS system	workflow and triggers the decision-making process for transient stability assessment.					
02	InterSCADA platform runs state estimation	Executes state estimation algorithm	The state estimation on the system is run, and a system state is available for further analysis	GET	State estimation engine	InterSCADA platform	I_02	
03	Events filtering	Executes the filtering engine for the whole contingency list.	The filtering method determines which events must be simulated with the time domain engine, and which ones don't lead to transient stability issues.	GET	Filtering engine	InterSCADA platform	I_03	
04	Network reduction/aggregation	Executes a network reduction/aggregation for each potentially dangerous event.	A network reduction/aggregation technique will be applied for each event classified as potentially dangerous by the events filtering method.	GET	Network reduction engine	InterSCADA platform	I_04	
05	Time-domain simulations	Executes a complete time-domain simulation for the potentially dangerous events	A time-domain simulation is conducted for each potentially dangerous event, using the reduced network identified in the previous step.	GET	Time-domain engine	InterSCADA platform	I_05	
06	Evaluation of margin estimations and countermeasures	Evaluates the margin estimations and the countermeasures.	Based on the results of the assessment part and the list of possible countermeasures provided by the system stability experts, making use of the possibilities given	GET	InterSCADA platform	InterSCADA platform	I_06	

Use case								
Use case name		Assess transient stability in real time						
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Inf. exchanged (IDs)	Requirements (IDs)
			by the power plant producers, the available margin for each scenario is calculated or the countermeasures needed. This step encompasses power flow calculations to create new system states as well as the previous steps mentioned for stability assessment (Steps 03, 04 and 05)					
07	Inform operators	Inform operators about the current risk related to transient stability	The decision-making process either sends an alarm to the operator in case of risky situations or at least provide the results with associated margins for all scenarios	CREATE	InterSCADA platform	Control room operator	I_07	

8.5. Information exchanged

Information exchanged			
Information exchanged, ID	Name of information exchanged	Description of information exchanged	Requirement, R-IDs
I_01	Measurements	(P, Q, V) measurements from the legacy SCADA system + system characteristics + topology information	
I_02	System state	A complete system state (V, theta for all nodes + targets for all components) is available for the rest of the workflow.	
I_03	List of potentially dangerous events	A list of scenarios with potential stability issues following the filtering stage	
I_04	Reduced system for each scenario	A reduced system for each scenario, following the network reduction stage	

<i>Information exchanged</i>			
<i>Information exchanged, ID</i>	<i>Name of information exchanged</i>	<i>Description of information exchanged</i>	<i>Requirement, R-IDs</i>
I_05	Dangerous scenario	A list of the dangerous scenarios at the end of the initial stability process.	
I_06	Margin estimations or necessary measures	Margin estimations or levers for each scenario	
I_07	Synthesis	Synthesis and detailed results for the control room operator	

9. Conclusions

This report has presented the results of Task 1.3 in work package 1 (WP1) in InterSCADA – “Pilots specification: use cases, datasets and key performance indicators” – providing technical overviews of the four demos and their associated use cases. In the four demos, 16 different use cases have been defined, all related to the control and operation of different examples of hybrid AC/DC power systems. Furthermore, the report describes how the final demo specifications have been shaped through collaboration among the WP partners and iterative improvements. The demos have been specified using a common template, ensuring consistency across the different demos and their use cases.

The report has also summarized the project’s key performance indicators (KPIs), focusing on aligning them with the demo KPIs and the other tasks and work packages of the project, and describing the necessary details on how the KPIs shall be operationalized.

